

ICIMOD

Final Report

**RAPID ASSESSMENT OF THE CONTEXT AND CURRENT
STATUS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AND
MANAGEMENT IN BANDARBAN**

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Acronyms

BBS	Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics
BGB	Border Guard of Bangladesh
BHDC	Bandarban Hill District Council
BPC	Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (NTO)
BSCIC	Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation
BTB	Bangladesh Tourism Board
BUET	Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology
CHTDB	Chittagong Hill Tracts Development Board
CHTDF	Chittagong Hill Tracts Development Facility (UNDP)
CHTRC	Chittagong Hill Tracts Regional Council
CPD	Centre for Policy Dialogue
CUET	Chittagong University of Engineering and Technology
DC	Deputy Commissioner
DTHM	Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management
DU	Dhaka University
GoB	Government of Bangladesh
ICIMOD	International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development
KSI	Khudra-Nrigoshthir Sanskritik Institute
LGED	Local Government Engineering Department
MoCAT	Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism
MoCHTA	Ministry of Chittagong Hill Tracts Affair
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NHTTI	National Hotel and Tourism Training Institute
PDB	Power Development Board
PPP	Public Private Partnership
REB	Rural Electrification Board
TCC	Tourism Carrying Capacity
TOAB	Tour Operators' Association of Bangladesh
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
VFR	Visiting Friends and Relatives

Executive Summary

Bandarban – ‘the roof of Bangladesh’, as described by the Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (the National Tourism Organization of Bangladesh), is a hidden paradise away from the din and bustle of the world. Though not developed for tourism activities yet, today or tomorrow it will be one of the paradises for eco-tourism. Undeniably, the number of tourists is increasing rapidly and this will continue in future.

Tourism is seasonal in pattern in Bandarban, and can be divided into peak and off-peak season. It has been estimated that almost half a million tourists visit Bandarban during peak season (Oct – March). And in off season (April – September) almost 0.15 million tourists visit Bandarban making a total of almost 0.65 to 0.70 million tourists per year. Though local farmers are busy with their winter vegetable cultivation during the peak season, they can manage time to work in the tourism industry. Moreover, a huge number of young people are unemployed, who will be happy to work in the tourism industry round the year.

As a rough estimate, if one tourist spends a minimum of Taka 1500 everyday on average, then the total receipt from tourism sector in Bandarban stands at around Taka 100 crore (12.5 million US \$).

From surveying tourists it was found that Bandarban is a destination for young people as it attracts them for adventure tourism. Majority of them (59.26%) fall into the age range between 25 and 34 years, followed by 33.33% into 15-24 years, and 7.41% into 45-54 years. Almost all of them visit Bandarban without taking any service from tour operator or travel agent. Most of them travel to Bandarban with their friend circle. Purpose of their visit is adventure and leisure (70% for adventure and 26% for leisure and recreation). Main motivation to visit Bandarban is seeing the serene hills and forest, enjoying the natural environment, adventure activities (mainly hill trekking, walking through Jhiripath or waterway to see waterfall in remote areas, and boating), and sensing peace and tranquillity.

Value chain mapping is an approach to show the flow of values to the ultimate customer- the tourist from the suppliers of tourism product and it includes supporting sectors also. For tourism development we must address the gaps in between different parties in the value chain. The tourism value chain in Bandarban generally integrates five main productive activities or sectors: accommodation, restaurants, transportation, handicrafts/shopping and tourism related services.

Government and private sector, along with other national and international organization, should involve local community and the tourists for the sustainable development of tourism in the paradise of Bandarban.

Tourism development is expected in Bandarban for the greater benefit of the local people- both the ethnic and non-ethnic. But it must be in a sustainable way without hampering the nature of this paradise and unique culture of the ethnic people and for their long-term economic benefit.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Bandarban is regarded as one of the most attractive travel destinations in Bangladesh. But no significant attempts have been made to explore and exploit this potential sector in Bandarban, except a small number of unplanned and scattered attempts. Consequently, the benefit of tourism has remained very limited for the local people. The purpose of the study was to assess the context and current status of tourism development and management in Bandarban. Further, another objective was to case-study the context and status of tourism in Ruma to review ongoing and to identify possible further involvement of the local communities in tourism through which they can upgrade their economic status. For that purpose, the structure of the tourism industry in Bandarban and Ruma including hotel, restaurant, transport, tour guides, and handicraft shops, tourists arrival and expenditure, motivation of the tourists etc. have been studied. Along with, Tourism Value Chain Mapping, SWOT analysis, identifying appropriate short and long term activities to develop tourism, and scope for interventions by different organizations and agencies were assessed with proper methodology.

ICIMOD plans to develop a pilot project for implementing the activities that will be shared together with the stakeholders and implemented in collaboration with the Ministry of Chittagong Hill Tracts Development Affairs, Government of Bangladesh, and a number of local organizations, private sector associations, and local community. These activities will enhance the benefits for mountain men and women of target groups in the pilot site by engaging them in the tourism sector. The objective of the pilot project is to reduce poverty among mountain men and women through increased resilience and unlocking of new livelihood opportunities. The focus of pilot project is to design and implement tourism activities in a collaborative manner that strengthen the economy of mountain people ensuring sustainable management of ecology and natural resources. The final beneficiaries of the project will be mountain communities. A strategy for sustainable tourism development and management in Bandarban will also be supported that will have the potential for replication in other districts of the Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT).

Study Objectives

In order to meet the aim of the project, the study pursues the three specific objectives:

- a) To gain an understanding of the context and current status of tourism development and management in Bandarban district of the Chittagong Hill Tracts.
- b) To look into a case of community involvement in tourism in Ruma sub-district of Bandarban district.
- c) To suggest a set of macro, meso and micro level interventions for initiating a pilot project by ICIMOD in Bandarban district with special focus on Ruma sub district.

Methodology

This study has used survey data as well as data from secondary sources. For the purposes of the study, the consultant visited Bandarban and Ruma along with two experienced data collectors, a tour operator, a resort owner, and the representative from ICIMOD from 14th August, 2013 to 28th August, 2013. During the mission, key tourism stakeholders – from officials to hoteliers, restaurant owners to farmers, local transport owners to craftsmen, and the tourists, –were interviewed to develop an understanding of local viewpoints on tourism and the flow of benefits from the sector. (See list of some key interviewees in Annex 5).

Data Collection:

Information was gathered using:

- Review of available documents
- Questionnaires
- Interviews of key stakeholders
- Opinion of the Govt. officials and local people (both ethnic and non-ethnic)
- Focus group discussion in Ruma

Data on demographics and poverty, ethnic diversity and spread, main economic sectors, tourism legislation and regulatory practice were basically from secondary sources.

Questionnaire Design:

Questionnaires were designed from that point of view that all data, needed for the purpose of the study, can be acquired from the questionnaires. Separate questionnaires were prepared for tourists, hotels, restaurants, local transports, and handicraft shops. (See Annex 7)

Study Area:

The study area was separated into two geographical zones:

Zone 1: Bandarban Sadar/Town (District headquarters)

Zone 2: Ruma (A sub-district of Bandarban district)

Sample Size:

Sampling was done on the basis of convenience and importance of the particular stakeholder.

Zone 1: In Bandarban Sadar, some 54 tourists' surveys were conducted. 92.6% of them are male. Most of them (59.26%) fall into the age range between 25-34 years, followed by 33.33% into 15-24 years, and 7.41% into 45-54 years. Most of the respondents surveyed in Bandarban Sadar are full-time employees (48.15%), followed by students (40.74%) and businessmen (11.11%). Only 11 persons of them (20%) are married.(See Annex 2 also).Total 10 hotels, 8 restaurants, 8 handicraft shops in Bandarban Sadar were surveyed.

Representatives of the only jeep owners' association, bus owners' association, and CNG owners' association were interviewed.

Zone 2: In Ruma, only 22 tourists were found for survey as it was off-peak season. 100% of them were male. 73% of them fall into the age range between 25-34 years; 18% into 45-54 years; and 9% into 15-24 years. Most of the respondents are full-time employees (64%), followed by businessmen (27%), and students (9%). 27% of them are married. (See Annex 2 also).

All the 8 hotels, 6 restaurants, 2 handicraft shops in Ruma Bazar were surveyed. Representatives of all the 2 boat owners' association and the only jeep owners' association were interviewed. 6 cottages in Boga Lake and 1 in Keokradong were also surveyed.

Motivations for visiting Bandarban and Ruma were determined from the opinion of tourists who were surveyed using SPSS version 11.5.

The main limitation was that no exhaustive study on tourism in Bandarban was available for reference. Existing tourism information is not recorded by the different agencies. Consequently it was difficult to collect tourism related data from secondary sources.

Chapter 2

Situational Analysis of Bandarban

Bandarban, in South-Eastern Bangladesh, is a district of the Chittagong Division under the region of Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT). CHT is a part of Hindu Kush Himalayan region. It is the second largest district of Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) having an area of 4,502 sq. km. The land composition of Bandarban is:

Figure 2.1: Land composition of Bandarban (source:)

Bandarban (meaning the dam of monkeys), or in Marma or Arakanese language as "Rwa-daw Mro" is also known as Arvumi or the Bohmong Circle (of the rest of the three hill districts Rangamati is the Chakma Circle and Khagrachari is the Mong Circle). Bandarban town is the home town of the Bohmong Chief¹ (currently King, or Raja, U Cha Truis Head of the Marma population).

It also is the administrative headquarter of Bandarban district, which has turned into one of the most exotic tourist attractions in Bangladesh since the insurgency in Chittagong Hill Tracts has ceased more than a decade back. Bandarban is not only the remotest district of the country, but also is the least populated.

The highest peaks of Bangladesh - Tahjindong (830 meters, also known as bijoy), Mowdok Mual (1052 m), and Keokradong (986 m), Saka Haphong (1063m) - are located in Bandarban district. Raikhiang Lake, the highest lake in Bangladesh is also situated here. Chimbuk peak and Boga Lake are two more highly noted attractions of the district. Bandarban is bordered by Cox's Bazaar, Chittagong, Rangamati and Khagrachari districts of Bangladesh. Other side of Bandarban lies with Myanmar provinces of Chin and Arakan. The district also features river Sangu, also known as Sangpo or Shankha, the only river born inside Bangladesh territory. Other two rivers in the district are Matamuhuri and Bakkhali. Meranja, Wailatong, Tambang and Politai are the four hill ranges here. Parts of the biggest lake in Bangladesh - Kaptai Lake – fall under the area of Bandarban².

¹ District portal of Bandarban district, LGED.

² Banglatrek (<http://www.banglatrek.org/>)

Figure 2.2: Map of Bandarban

Demographics and Poverty:

Distribution of Population:

There are 388335 people living in Bandarban. The district has a wide variety in tribal group. There are seven Sub-districts(upazila) in Bandarban. The most populous sub-district is Lama and the least populous sub-district is Thanchi. Thanchi is considered to be the most backward sub-district in Bandarban. It is the biggest sub-district of Bandarban but having least population. In BandarbanSadar, Lama &Alikadam there is a combination of Bengali people and the tribal people. But in other Sub-district there is the presence of mainly the tribal people.

East sided sub-districts (Rowangchori, Ruma&Thanchi) which are closer to the border have undeveloped infrastructure. This is the main reason behind the lower density of population within the district. But these three districts have a lot of potentials regarding tourism as they have a lot of beautiful destination.

According to the census of 2011

The distribution of population in percentage can be shown in the pie chart below:

Figure 2.3: Distribution of population

Poverty Mapping across the district:

Regional difference of the income level of people of Bangladesh is very acute. Bandarban is one of those districts of Bangladesh which suffers from poverty a lot. Across the district there is also the presence of the difference in the level of income of the people as there is a great difference in the level of infrastructural development. 37-55% population of four Sub-districts (Alikadam, Ruma, Thanchi & Lama) are living below the poverty line.

Figure 2.4: Poverty Maps (Source: Local estimation of poverty and Malnutrition in Bangladesh 2004, The Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics.)

At Bandarban Sadar and Rowangchhari less than 25% of the total populations are living below the poverty line.

Bandarban is unique from other districts in terms of availability of some unique resources like tourist destination, and diversified ethnicity which can be branded to promote tourism. There is scope for diversified economic activities too. When the people will get the chance to involve themselves with different types of activities they will be able to earn more than before which will leverage the district to get out of poverty. Considering the natural beauty along with diversified ethnic lifestyle and culture, tourism can be the number one economic activity in Bandarban to alleviate their socio-economic status.

Ethnic Diversity and Spread:

Ethnic Nationals:

There are eleven ethnic nationals living in Bandarban. They are:

MARMA, MURONG, TRIPURA, BAWM, TANCHANGYA, CHAKMA, CHAK, KHYANG, KHUMI, PANKONE (LUSHEI) and the PANKHO. Out of 11 tribal groups, Marma, Murong, and Tripura are the largest in number. The distribution of the major tribal people in Bandarban along with Bengali people in respect of Sub-districts (according to BBS Census 2011) is given below:

Table 2.1: Distribution of Major Tribal people in Bandarban

Name of the Sub-district	Bengali	Ethnic minority/Tribal people					Total Ethnic minority/Tribal	Total Population
		Marma	Mro	Tripura	Others			
Alikadam	27990	4046	11599	3079	2603	21327	49317	
Bandarban Sadar	48470	22978	5829	1423	9582	39812	88282	
Lama	81989	13752	7267	5314	673	27006	108995	
Naikhongchhari	50206	4351	1822	305	5104	11582	61788	
Rowangchhari	2519	14300	1292	2019	7134	24745	27264	
Ruma	2595	9598	5364	3002	8539	26503	29098	
Thanchi	2165	8452	4848	5543	2583	21426	23591	
Total	215934	77477	38021	20685	36218	172401	388335	

Source: Table Bangladesh Population Census 2011, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics

Figure 2.5 : Pictorial presentation of the above table excluding Bengali people.*

Source: Developed by the team, 2013.

Main Economic Sectors and Sources of Income:

Main economic sectors across the district:

Bandarban experiences widespread Jumm farming (slash and burn agricultural technique), but Jumm farming produces little and mostly used for self-consumption of the hill people. Fruits (banana, pineapple, jackfruit, papaya), and spices (masala) like ginger, and turmeric are also produced in Bandarban. A little bit of cashew nuts and oranges are also being produced in some parts of Bandarban. Tribal textile is one of the major exportable of the district. Clothes are mostly made of cotton, wool imported from Myanmar. All cotton is spun and woven by hand. Presently Tourism is growing fast as a source of revenue.

Bamboo and tobacco grows in significant quantity. Bamboo and cane are used to make the traditional stilt houses.

In recent years especially after 2000, tourism in Bandarban is emerging as one of the main economic activities. Although we could not get reliable data on tourist expenditure in Bandarban, but during our field survey it has been estimated that almost 100 crore (1 billion) Taka is pumped into this hill district from tourism sector. It is visualized that in future tourism will be the number one source of earning money by the local people.

Md. Jamaluddin in his study on “Identifying Livelihood Patterns of Ethnic Minorities and their Coping Strategies Different Vulnerabilities Situation in Chittagong Hill Tracts Region, Bangladesh” has shown main income sources of different tribal groups of Bandarban (Jamaluddin. 2010). The following diagram shows these sources of income:

Figure 2.6: The economic activities of the people of Bandarban on the basis of Sample Survey by Jamaluddin et al, 2010 (reproduced by the team, 2013)

Source: Jamaluddin et al, 2010 (Reproduced by the team, 2013)

It is revealed from the study that major part of income of the ethnic households comes from three main sources like day labour, fruit gardening, and Jumm cultivation. It has also been observed that weightage on different income sources highly varied from one ethnic group to another. Bawms, for example are more dependent on fruit gardening, whereas Chakma, Marma, Tanchanga, and Tripura tribes are mostly day labourers. The Mro people are lucky to depend more on remittance.

Till today, agriculture is the most significant economic sector to the Bandarban people. The following table shows the agri-produces and use of land:

Table2.2 : The major agriculture products and the land used for the production in Bandarban district.

Production of Agriculture product and Used area			
Serial no	Name of Items	Area(acre)	Production(MetricTon)
1.	Tobaco	4,362	3,356
2.	Fish Catch	539	299
3.	Onion	66	64
4.	Rice	44,344	50,057
5.	Sugar Cane	141	2,433
6.	Eggs(pcs)		360,169
7.	Milk		52
8.	Pulse	307	128
9.	Vegetable	4143	6212
10.	Sweet Meat	2	211
11.	Turmaric	1515	3431
12.	Garlic	395	1020
13.	Tea	129	0

Source: Zila profile of Bandarban; Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. 2007

Figure2.7: The percentages of production of different agriculture products are shown in the pie chart below*:

*Pie chart developed by the Team.

However, over the last one and half decades, importance of agriculture in economy is gradually lessening and the service sector is flourishing tremendously. The following table show the trend:

Table 2.3: Trends in GDP in current market price (in Million US\$) 1995/96 to 2005/06

Sector	1995/96	2005/2006
Agriculture	36	19 (-)
Industrial GDP	12	20 (+)
Service Sector	45	66 (+)
Crop	26	8 (-)
Livestock	5	4 (-)
Fisheries	1	1
Forestry	4	5 (+)

Source: Uttam Deb *et al*, CPD 2008

A few number of international agencies and NGOs are working in the district to alleviate the economic condition of the tribal people. The following Figure shows the successes of the agencies:

Table 2.4: Local economic development activities by UNDP-Chittagong Hill Tracts Development Facility, DANIDA , CIDA, USAID AND OTHERS.

1. 16 weavers group have been trained to use natural fibres and dyeing methods.
2. 2348 producers have been trained entrepreneurial skills
3. 2244 households have diversified their income by cultivating mushrooms, honey bee keeping. Bio briquette, and ginger processing.
4. Arranging linkage building workshops and agro product fairs.
5. Value chain assessment of banana, turmeric, and pineapple.

Source: UNDP-CHTDF study.

The efforts by several international donor agencies and NGOs are playing important role in diversifying the income sources of the tribal people of Bandarban. But no such organizations are seen to invest in tourism sectors where people can be benefitted more in terms of income. By financing camping grounds, training the tribal people in house- keeping, cooking and

hospitality, performing cultural shows, handicrafts, etc. could tremendously increase income of different communities in different camping spots.

Main Distribution Markets:

There are twenty one main distribution market in Bandarban through which all the products are sold. Seven of them are at Bandarban Sadar. The distribution markets are:

Sub-districts	Name of markets
Alikadam	1. Alikadam Bazar
Bandarban Sadar	1. Bandarban Bazar 2. Balaghata Bazar 3. Ravilla Bazar 4. Kemolong Bazar 5. Bagmara Bazar 6. Chemimukh Bazar 7. Reicha Bazar
Lama	1. Lama Bazar 2. Dalukhari Bazar
Rowangchhari	1. Rowangchhchari Bazar
Naikhongchhari	1. Naikhongchhari Bazar 2. Dochari Bazar 3. Baishari Bazar 4. Nuton Bazar 5. Tombrue Bazar 6. Gondum Bazar
Ruma	1. Ruma Bazar 2. Ghalangya Bazar
Thanchi	1. Thanchi Bazar 2. Bolipara Bazar

Source: From Field survey, 2013

The markets are important for the backward and forward linkages of all type of products. The spatial distribution of markets shows the economic zones of the area. The following figure shows the concentration of markets in different zones of Bandarban.

Figure 2.8 : The map below is representing the distribution markets within Bandarban:

Position of tourism as an economic sector:

There is no specific information on the position of tourism as an economic sector in Bandarban. But from our field observation and on the basis of field survey it seems to be the third most contributing sector in the economy after agriculture and day labour.

How many tourists visit Bandarban? This question was raised to different government and local authorities including the Deputy Commissioner, Bandarban Hill District Council, Superintendent of Police etc. We also tried to get an idea of the number of tourists visiting Bandarban from different data sources like BPC, MoCHTA, Wikipedia, several blogs etc. But unfortunately we could not make any breakthrough. Later, we got some approximate estimation on the number of tourist coming to Bandarban from the Bandarban Hoteliers Association, Bangladesh Police, Bandarban, and the BGB check posts.

Tourism is seasonal in pattern in Bandarban, and can be divided into peak and off-peak season.

Pick season (Oct – March): On average everyday 3000 tourists enter into Bandarban. This means that almost half a million tourists visit Bandarban during season.

Off season: On week-end (Friday & Saturday) almost 1500 tourists and on other week days around 500 tourists come to Bandarban. Beside, during two Eids (Muslim festivals) additional 40,000 tourists come to Bandarban. Taking the data into consideration we can roughly say that during off-season, almost 150,000 tourists visit Bandarban making a total of almost 0.65 to 0.70 million tourists per year.

Therefore, it can be estimated that around 7 hundred thousand tourists each year visit Bandarban. If one tourist spends a minimum of Taka 1500 everyday on average, total money pumped into Bandarban from tourism sector stands at Taka 100 crore (equivalent US\$ 12.5 million).

Day by day the total number of tourist arrival is increasing. It is hoped that it will continue, as a craze has been developed within the tourist to spend their leisure time in Bandarban.

With diversified and quality services offered to the tourists, tourism can be the single most contributing sector in the economy of Bandarban. Though local farmers are busy with their winter vegetable cultivation during the peak season, they can manage time to work in the tourism industry. Moreover, a huge number of young people are unemployed, who will be happy to work in the tourism industry round the year.

Chapter 3

Political and Legal Environment for Tourism Development

Tourism Legislations and Regulatory practices:

Bangladesh has a few number of tourism related laws. The main laws are:

1. The Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (BPC) Order – 1972
(Bangladesh Tourism Corporation)
2. The Bangladesh Parjatan Board Law – 2010
(Bangladesh Tourism Board)
3. The Bangladesh Reserved Area Tourism Law – 2010
4. Bangladesh Hotel and Restaurant Law -2013
5. Besamarik Biman Chalachal Kortripoksho Ain (Civil Aviation Authority Act) - 2013
6. Bangladesh Travel Agency (Registration and Control) Act -2013

The BPC Order of 1972 was formulated keeping in mind the state policy of the new borne country. As per the law Bangladesh Tourism Corporation was created to look after the tourism and hospitality sector. However, with the change of state policy, specially moving from socialistic economic concept to free market economic concept, the role and responsibility of BPC were deemed to be inadequate and outdated to coup up with the changed national and international economic vis-à-vis tourism sectors. Consequently, The Bangladesh ParjatanBoard (Bangladesh Tourism Board) Law was enacted in 2010. Subsequently, other tourism related Laws concerning reserved area tourism, hotel and restaurant, travel agencies, tour guides, taxi cabs etc. were formed, amended, and enacted.

In any of the laws, nothing has been specifically mentioned about tourism policy in Hill districts of Bangladesh. However, in the Chittagong Hill Tracts Peace Accord of 1997, the local tourism has been vested in the hands of Bandarban Hill District Council (BHDC) (vide article no. 34-f).

The BPC has established one motel called “Meghala Parjatan Motel” at the outskirt of Bandarban sadar (district town level) and another resort has been created by the Bangladesh Army at Nilgiri – some 45 kilometers away from Bandarban. The district authority, Police department, and the Zilla Parishad have also created some accommodation

units mainly for the departmental use or of use by the government officials. A few number of motels and hotels have been established by the private entrepreneurs mainly around the municipal area. Apart, no significant activities relating to tourism and hospitality have been done by any public or private sector.

Few years before, there had been some insurgency problems in the hill districts which restricted the free entrance and movement of the civilians from other areas. Consequently, the enormous tourism sector of the area was untapped. However, with the enactment of Peace Accord in 1997, the domestic tourists were allowed to get in up to certain spatial radius. At present the situation has been much improved and the domestic visitors are allowed to go into remote areas of hill districts with permission from the Border Guard Bangladesh (BGB) – a paramilitary force of the government.

Regarding the investment climate in tourism sector, till now no favorable situation could be seen because of two reasons mainly:

- (a) Before 1997 Peace Accord, economic and business activities were almost at a halt, and
- (b) After 1997 Peace Accord, the land management including sale, purchase, lease, transfer etc. has been vested in the hands of the District Council. The article no. 26 of the accord says :

“..... no land, including those land suitable for giving settlement, within the boundaries of Hill District shall be given in settlement including giving lease, purchased, sold, and transferred without prior approval of the Council ...”

This provision of the accord does not encourage the investors to come up with big investment in economic and business sectors including tourism. As a result, in spite of having greater opportunity for establishing SMEs in the fields of food processing, tourism and travelling, accommodation etc. the hill district is lagging behind.

Business Environment

In the present context, because of so many reasons, the tourism business in Bandarban is not that much big in comparison to Cox’s Bazar. Cox’s Bazar cannot be considered as a competitor of Bandarban. Cox’s Bazar is endowed with sun, sea and sand; Bandarban is gifted with green serene hills, serpentine hilly roads, wonderful combination of varied ethnic cultural rituals etc. These two destinations are having different characteristics.

But unfortunately, tourism could not flourish in Bandarban because the territory was blocked long time after the independence of Bangladesh. Now the time has come to explore and

exploit the tourism sector of this hill district through which the livelihoods of the local people will improve tremendously and sustainably.

At present no pro-active tourism business associations or other formal group like tour operator could be found who are working to develop and promote tourism in the hill district. However, in the district headquarter, Bandarban Hotel owners' association, Restaurant owners' association, Jeep-Car owners' association, Bus owners' association, Boat owners' association, Tour Guides association are in existence. But they perform more to solve their business problems rather than thinking about development of tourism in the long run.

Dhaka based Tour operators are conducting tour programs to Bandarban. According to TOAB (Tour Operators' Association of Bangladesh) only 15 to 20 tour operators of Dhaka are regularly conducting tour programs including trekking and sight- seeing in Bandarban.

Licensing: To establish a tourism business in Bandarban, one has to apply for a trade license from Bandarban district administration. For setting a business outside the district Sadar area, one has to seek license from Union Council or Sub-district Council.

For setting up a tourism business in Bandarban Hill District one has to go through a lengthy procedure. Entrepreneur from outside Bandarban cannot purchase land in Bandarban Hill District freely. Therefore only the local people are allowed to commence a business with some permanent structure and establishment. Like in other districts the entrepreneur has to take permission from the Municipal authority and the BHDC. However authentication process as a local inhabitant is very lengthy which involves the Deputy Commissioner of the district, Headman of the area, local Karbari, or the King. Finally if the BHDC finds it satisfactory, forwards it to the Chittagong Hill Tracts Regional Council.

Competition: The main competitor of Bandarban is Rangamati followed by KhagraChhari, as these destinations offer same tourism products. Rangamati and KhagraChhari are also hill tracts with so many hills and water falls, huge lakes, green hilly forests with so many different wild animals and birds, and so many different amazing tribal communities, that make these destinations popular to the tourists and thus they compete with Bandarban. **However, Bandarban has somehow emerged as an unparalleled hilly destination keeping behind Rangamati and Khagrachhari. Existence of the highest peak of Bangladesh, huge adventurous Trekking opportunity, dreamy Army resort at Nilgiri, beautiful private resorts of Sakura and Milanchhari, and the proactive efforts by**

different wings of the district administration, and BHDC have turned Bandarban as the number one hill tourist destination.

Cox's Bazar, the longest sea beach in the world, is another major competitor of Bandarban. Though it does not offer the same natural attraction, but yet, Cox's Bazar is the main tourist spot in Bangladesh and competes with destination of any feature in Bangladesh. Cox's Bazar is better in terms of tourism infrastructures and ease of access. It attracts tourists for white sandy beach where one can see the endless sea.

Tourism related Business Associations

Tourism in Bandarban is not mature enough to have strong business association for tourism development. In Bandarban, there is no formal tourism business association. In Bandarban Sadar, there are so many business associations that may be termed those are active for their own business interest, but are the directly involved with tourism. These associations are-

- Hotel Owners' Association
- Jeep-Car Owners' Association
- Bus Owners' Association
- Boat Owners' Association
- Restaurant Owners' Association
- Tour Guide Association
- Tribal Cultural Society

In different sub-districts and specific tourist spots, there are some local tribal associations and cultural groups who are involved in tourism development and promotion, but in an unplanned way and in insignificant level. Some NGOs are promoting handicrafts (Viator Bangladesh Ltd., Eengmak etc.).

Chapter 4

Tourism Zones and Attractions of Bandarban

Bandarban – *‘the roof of Bangladesh’*, as described by the Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (the National Tourism Organization of Bangladesh), is a hidden paradise away from the hustle and bustle of the world. Its flora and fauna, hills and forests, craggy waterfalls and zigzag rivers, bamboo cottages of its ethnic people and their lifestyle have made this picturesque hill tract a popular eco-tourism destination of tourists from home and abroad.

The world’s leading tourism magazine ‘Lonely Planet’ succinctly describes this majestic destination’s appeal as follows:³

“Put simply there is no better place in which to experience the magic of the Hill Tracts than in the small town of Bandarban, which lies on the Sangu River, 92km from Chittagong. The river is the center of local life: bamboo rafts up to 500m long, steered by a single solitary boatman, drift leisurely downstream, while country boats make slow trips to neighboring villages. Most inhabitants belong to the Buddhist Marma tribe. The town itself, which has a couple of interesting sights, isn’t overly attractive, but the surrounding countryside is some of the finest in Bangladesh and offers one of the few opportunities to really escape the masses. Instead of the honking of horns and awe-struck stares of the masses you’ll have nothing much to listen to but birdsong and the only things likely to be fluttering about you will be bright, floppy winged butterflies. All up this is not a town to rush through in a hurry.”

Though not developed for tourism activities yet, today or tomorrow it will be one of the paradises for eco-tourism, and the adventure lovers will find the meaning of life in roaming around in the natural wilderness of this hilly district.

*Photos of (from left to right) Meghla lake, Buddha DhatuJedi, and Bandarban lake
(Photo source: Wikipedia)*

³<http://www.lonelyplanet.com/bangladesh/chittagong-division/bandarban#ixzz2anshBulD>

Zones for tourism development: Tourism and only Tourism

Though the entire Bandarban district is a tourist destination, some zoning for tourism can be done on the basis of more visits by the tourist and tourism development potentials. However, the main tourist attractions fall within three sub-districts namely: Bandarban, Ruma and Thanchi. The dotted area in following map shows the zones for tourism development. In the following paragraphs we present some of the attractive places and spots in Bandarban.

Figure 4.1: Zones for tourism development in Bandarban

Tourist Areas/Attractions in Bandarban

Meghla Tourist Spot: Meghla Parjatan Complex is one of the most amazing tourist spots in Bandarban on the gateway of Bandarban maintained by district administration. It is 4 km from the town. It is a popular place for picnic party as it features a mini-safari-park, a zoo, boat journey, hanging bridge and artificial lake at the bottom of the hills.

Photo source: pictureworld.com

Golden Temple: Golden Temple or the Buddha DhatuJadi is a Theravada Buddhist temple known as the Shorno Mondir to the tourists of Bangladesh. It is located at Pulpara, 10 kilometer from the Bandarban hill district. It is the largest Theravada Buddhist Temple with the second largest Buddha statue in Bangladesh. The Golden Temple is considered as one of the holy site for Theravada Buddhism followers and Buddhist pilgrims.

Photo source: wordpress.com

Sangu River: The River Sangu (also known as Sangpo or Shankha), is the only river born inside Bangladesh territory. It crisscrossed the whole Bandarban on her way. The length of the river is 295 km. Boat ride on the river Sangu is one of the main attractions here for tourists.

Photo source: wikitravel.org

Nilachal Tourist Spot: From the top of Nilachal one can have a total glimpse of Bandarban town and a vast landscape of hillside. Nilachal is situated at Tigerpara 5 kilometer away from the Bandarban town and about 2000 feet above the sea level. The view of the landscape from the top of the Nilachal is so spectacular for snapping.

Photo source: blogspot.com

Nilgiri (Hilltop resort): Nilgiri is the highest tourist spot of Bangladesh about 3500ft high from the sea level. It is situated in Thanchiupzilla, just 45km away from Bandarban Sadar and maintained by Bangladesh Army. It is just 45km away from Bandarbandsadar. The colorful culture and living style of Mro of nearby village are surely an unexplored experience to tourists. In rainy season the whole spot is covered with the blanket of clouds.

Photo source: banglaview24.com

ShoilaPropat (Waterfall): This is one of the most visited natural falls of Bangladesh, 4 km from the town on the road to Thanchiat Milanchari. The rocky pathway to this spot will involve several ascents and descents along hillside. The flow of this fall becomes vigorous during the rainy season; one can hear the purl of this fall throughout the year. The water of this fall is so transparent and cool and is a good source for drinking water and household use for the local bawm community.

Photo source: gstatic.com

Chimbuk Hill: Chimbuk, called as the Darjeeling of Bengal, is a unique hill having different kinds of tourist attractions. It's about 2500ft high above sea level and is just 26 kilometer away from Bandarbandsadar. The top of this hill is plain and it is like a plateau and one will definitely be charmed having glimpses of the zigzag way heading to chimbuk.

Photo source: panoramio.com

Tourism Growth Trends and Opportunities

Bandarban has become a hot cake to tourists for the last few years. All the four highest peaks of Bangladesh - Tahjindong (830 meters, also known as bijoy), MowdokMual (1052 meters), and Keokradong (986 metres), SakaHaphong (1063meters) - are located in Bandarban district, as well as Raikhiang Lake, the highest lake in Bangladesh.⁴ There are more than

⁴Wikipedia

fifteen ethnic minorities living in the district besides the Bengalis, including: the Bomong, Marma, Mru, Tanchangya, Khyang, Tripura, Lushei, Khumi, Chak, Kuki, Chakma, Rakhine or Arakanese, Riyang, Usui and Pankho. Law and order situation in Bandarban is simply the best in Bangladesh.

Though reliable historical data are not available, but still it can be said confidently that the growth in tourism sector is faster than any other economic sector in Bandarban.

Number of hotels is increasing in Bandarban for the three or four years. As stated by the owner of 'Hotel Four Star', a renowned hotel in Bandarban, the number of hotels in Bandarban Sadar (town) is increasing as shown in the following table:

Year	2010	2011	2012	2013
No. of Hotel	30	35	40	42

Though this table does not describe the actual figures, rather than round figures, the situation is not so much different from it. Most of the hotel owners, including the president of the hotel owners' association, think that the number of hotel in Bandarban will continue to increase as the number of tourists is increasing day by day.

The occupancy rate is also increasing in hotels and it will continue in future. Number of restaurant and transports are increasing rapidly to meet the increased demand.

It is found from survey that almost all the tourists visiting Bandarban will revisit and recommend Bandarban.

New tourist spots are being explored and tourists are quite curious to visit these spots. Adventure tourism is a new concept to Bangladeshi tourists, and Bandarban is the one of few destinations for adventure tourism. Different remote spots are being explored by the drifters and soon these are becoming so popular that many others are getting interested to visit these places. Even now, some spots are unexplored by the tourists.

The concept of trekking tourism in different trails and homestay will be a breakthrough for tourism in Bandarban. Planned tourism development in trekking trails and the provision for homestay in adjacent villages can change the economic condition of poor tribal people living in remote areas. This is the most potential tourist destination that will certainly flourish in near future.

Chapter 5

Structure of the Tourism Industry

Review of Accommodation in Bandarban District

Bandarban has been recently so popular destination among the Bangladeshi tourists. As a result the number of hotel has been increasing for the last few years, specifically for the last three years. Though the hotels are concentrated mainly in Bandarban Sadar, the number of hotel is increasing in Sub-districts like Ruma and Thanchi, which are popular for some unique natural attractions.

Type of Accommodation: In Bandarban, hotel is the main form of accommodation facility followed by some so-called guest houses and newly developed resorts.

Number of Accommodation: In Bandarban Sadar (District Head-quarter) the number of hotel, motel, resort, and guesthouse is 42 with 3500 beds altogether.⁵ In Ruma this number is 15 with 500 beds altogether; including 8 hotels in Ruma Bazar, 6 cottages in Boga Lake, and 1 cottage in Keokradong. In Thanchi there are 2 and in Lama there are 5 hotels.⁶

Table 5.1 : Number of Hotel, motel etc. in the district of Bandarban.

Sub-district	No. of hotel, motel, resort, and guesthouse	No. of Beds
Bandarban Sadar	42	3500
Ruma	15	500 (approx.)
Thanchi	2-3	70-80 (approx.)
Lama	4-5	100-120 (approx.)
Ali Kodom	6-8	150-180 (approx.)

Source: Field survey 2013

Price Range: Price range can be categorized according the type of accommodation. From the hotel survey the following price range is summarized:

Hotel	Budget: BDT 150-300 Mid-range: BDT 300-1500 Classy: BDT 1000-4000
Resort	BDT 3000-6000
Guest House	BDT 1000-3000

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Occupancy throughout the year: Tourism in Bandarban is seasonal in pattern. Tourists visit Bandarban in winter specifically from October to March. Especially after the Eid-ul-Fitre and Eid-ul-Azha, people from different part of the country come to Bandarban to enjoy their vacation. In peak season from October to March the average occupancy rate is around 60% to

⁵Bandarban Hotel, Motel, Guest house Owners' Association, Bandarban.

⁶Bandarban Hotel, Motel, Guest house Owners' Association, Bandarban.

80%. But in off-peak season the occupancy rate is 20% to 40% in whole district. But, there is a difference in occupancy rate regarding the class of the hotels in Bandarban Sadar.

Class of Hotel	Occupancy Rate (%)	
	Peak season	Off-Peak season
Budget	80%-100%	40%-50%
Mid-range	60%-80%	20%-30%
Classy	50%-60%	0%-10%

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

We should keep in mind that the reason for relatively high occupancy rate for the budget hotels during the off-peak season is the overnight stay by the local people. As most of the administrative buildings are concentrated in Bandarban Sadar, local people have to come here round the year for different purpose from different remote areas and other sub-districts of Bandarban and they prefer these budget hotels.

This occupancy rate is gradually increasing though in 2013 the occupancy rate is less than that in the previous years due to political unrest.

Review of Food and Beverage Facilities in Bandarban District

In Bandarban district Food and Beverage Establishments can be categorized into two broad types-

- Restaurant with heavy food item (rice) for lunch and dinner
- Small light-food shop and tea stall with no rice item

The number of these enterprises is increasing for the last three or four years as the number of tourists are increasing day by day.

	No. of Restaurant with heavy food item	No. of Small light food shop and tea stall	Total
Bandarban Sadar	25	5	30
Bandarban District	80	40	120

Source: Bandarban Restaurant Owners' Association.

Type of food served: Restaurants serving rice for lunch and dinner offer fish curry, chicken curry, mutton curry, beef curry, and vegetables. They offer Ruti, Porota, egg, vegetable, soup, and tea for breakfast. Some of these restaurant offer Chicken Biryani, Mutton Biryani, and Beef Biryani.

Small light food shops do not offer lunch or dinner, rather they offer light food like soup, porota, grilled chicken, ruti, vegetable, fruit juice, and tea. But these types of shops are found only in Bandarban Sadar. Other small food shops are mainly tea stall offering bread and banana with cigarette. There are some other sweetmeat shops that also fall in this category.

Price range: If someone wants to have his/her lunch or dinner with three item (vegetable + chicken/fish/beef + dal) in restaurants he/she will be charged BDT 120-150. Restaurants charge 150 to 180 taka for Biryani.

Review of Tour Agencies and Guides in Bandarban District

In Bandarban the number of tour agency and tour operator is very limited as most of the tourists prefer to visit Bandarban with their own plan. Even often tourists come to Bandarban with no plan of which places they will visit. They gather information from hotels or transports about the places must visit and decide instantly. Moreover, visiting a particular spot is often uncertain as the Police, the Army and the BGB (Border Guard of Bangladesh) often impose restriction upon visiting particular spots for the safety and security purpose. Very little information can be found about tour operators offering tour package for Bandarban. The Guide Tour Ltd., Tour Planner Ltd. and few other tour operators offer packages to tourists specially for trekking in winter season. Some tour operators plan tour when a large group of tourists request a tour package for them. Other large tour operators are still not interested about Bandarban as it is still a destination for young students who don't need any tour operator for planning the tour for them. Tourists, who are going for trekking, must take a local tour guide. They must seek permission from the Police or the Army check-point when they are to go for trekking and at the time of entry they must have a local tour guide, otherwise they won't be allowed for trekking. These local tour guides are well experienced and are available in the spots or in the Army check-point. The rate for different spot is fixed by the authority.

Review of Transportation in Bandarban District

Bus, jeep (ChanderGari), and CNG auto rickshaw are the main types of local transport for the transportation of local people and tourists within Bandarban. As Bandarban is a hilly area other vehicles are not suitable. Rickshaws are available only in Bandarban Sadar.

Bus: Total 34 buses are operated in different routes of Bandarban. All these buses are owned by different individual owners who are the members of Bandarban Bus Owners' Association.

Route	No. of Bus operated	Rate in BDT (per seat)
BandarbanSadar- Thanchi(Bolipara)	6	160-200
Bandarban Sadar - Ruma	10	100
BandarbanSadar- Ruangchhori	6	50
BandarbanSadar –Bangalkhali - Rangamati	12	130

Source: Bandarban Bus Owners' Association.

Number of seat of each bus is 36. Total number of people working in these buses including driver, helper, ticket seller, and line-man is around 600.(*Source: Bandarban Bus Owners' Association.*)

Jeep (Chander Gari): In Bandarban, Chander Gari is the most perfect transport for hilly roads. Chander Gari is actually old Military Jeeps that were used by the Pakistan Army before 1971 in Bangladesh. But now these types of jeeps are very useful in Bandarban for local people and tourists to reach their distant destinations. Land cruisers, Nissan Patrols, and Hi-aces are also common in Bandarban; in fact all these cars are operated under the same owner's association namely 'Bandarban Jeep – Car – Microbus Owners' Association.'

Type of Car	No. of Vehicles	No. of Seats (each car)	Total sitting capacity
ChanderGari	85	14	1190
Land cruiser	10	5	50
Land cruiser-2 (local name: 5-doors)	20	7	140
Hi-ace	10	14	140
Nissan Patrol	20	7	140
Total	145		1650

Source: Bandarban Jeep – Car – Microbus Owners' Association.

These cars are operated in different routes within Bandarban and Bandarban to other districts.

- BandarbanSadar –ShoiloPropat – Chimbuk – Neel Giri – Thanchi
- BandarbanSadar – Ruma – Boga Lake – Keokradong – Tajingdong
- BandarbanSadar – RuangChhori
- Bandarban Sadar – Lama Sub-district
- BandarbanSadar – Ali Kodom Sub-district
- BandarbanSadar – NaikkhongChhori Sub-district
- Bandarban Sadar – Chittagong District
- BandarbanSadar – Rangamati District

The rates are different for different type of vehicle subject to the destination on the basis of contract. Total number of people working in these car including driver, helper, and line-man is around 300.⁷

CNG Auto Rickshaw: CNG Auto Rickshaws are recently getting popularity over bus and jeep. At present the number of CNG Auto Rickshaw is 350 (CNG Auto Rickshaw 200 + Mahindra Auto Rickshaw 150).

Type of Vehicle	No. of Vehicles	No. of seats (each vehicle)	Total seats
CNG Auto Rickshaws	200	3	600
Mahindra	150	4	600
Total	350		1200

Source: Bandarban CNG– Mahindra Owners' Association.

⁷Bandarban Jeep – Car – Microbus Owners' Association.

These auto rickshaws are very flexible in term of route, that is, one may reach exactly where he/she wants to, where buses take people only to the bus stands. These auto rickshaws are operated in different routes of Bandarban, Ruma, Thanchi, RuangChhori, Baghmara, Keranihat, Chondroghona, Ali Kadam, Lama, Fasiakhali, and NaikkhongChorri.

Engine Boat: During the rainy season, when roads are broken due to heavy rain, road transports become useless in different remote areas of Bandarban. This time engine boats become the major transportation mode in Bandarban as the river Sangu and Matamuhuri are full to the brims at this time and engine boat can connect different remote areas as these rivers are very meandering in their ways.

Review of Handicraft shops in Bandarban District

Handicrafts, specially wooden and woolen products made by tribal people, are very popular among the tourists. The reason behind the popularity is the uniqueness of the product, tribal design, and superior quality.

Type of Handicrafts: Handicrafts made by the tribal people basically are of three types-woolen, wooden, and textile.

Woolen products: Hilly Blanket, Muffler, Shawl, Bed-cover, Bag, Nokshi Katha etc.

Textile: Thami (tribal dress for woman), Salwar-Kamij (Bengali dress for woman), Orna, Shirt, Panjabi, Fotua, Dress for children etc.

Wooden products: Tume (tribal water pot), Throng (tribal basket for woman), Bamboo water pot, Mug, Cup, Tray, Pencil box, Key ring etc.

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

All the items are hand-made without using any electric machine. Tribal women make these products at their home during their leisure time. But most of them do not have sales outlet for their own. As a result they cannot sell their products to the tourists. They can sell their products only to those tourists who visit their village and show interest to buy these products. Basically, these village craftsmen make these handicrafts for their own use, but they are always ready to sell these if anyone offers real price for these.

Some craftsmen have their own shop in local markets. Often the shopkeepers sell their own products; but in peak season they collect handicrafts from individual craftsmen from nearby villages to meet the demand. Though there are some handicraft factories in Bandarban established and operated by some commercial enterprises (Hill KaruPonno with 13 branches) and some NGOs (Viator Bangladesh Ltd., Eengmak etc.) tribal people do not take it as their permanent profession as the demand for their products is seasonal as tourism is seasonal in Bandarban. Local entrepreneurs are getting discouraged due to the seasonality of demand and marketing constraints.

Number of Sales Outlet: The total number of handicraft shop is around 25 in Bandarban and 20 of them are in Bandarban Sadar. Shops in Bandarban Sadar are operated by commercial enterprises and NGOs those have their own factories and permanent craftsmen working in these factories. These craftsmen have taken it as their profession and do not do any other job. But, shops outside, in sub-districts are operated by individual craftsmen as their attempt for self-employment.

Location of the outlets	No. of outlets
Bandarban Sadar	20
Ruma	2
Thanchi	1
RuangChhori	1

Source: Bandarban Chamber of Commerce and Industry.

Tourists can buy tribal handicrafts directly from the individual craftsmen when they visit craft villages and obviously at a cheaper price.

Backward Linkage of the Tourism Industry

Food and Beverage Sector: Restaurants purchase vegetables, fishes, beef, chicken, mutton and other grocery items from local people and outside Bandarban. Though vegetables are locally supplied, other items are brought mainly from Chittagong.

Sources of Input Supplies of Food & Beverage Sector in Bandarban	
Locally Resourced*	Brought from Outside
Vegetables	Rice (from Jessore& Chittagong)
Chicken (hilly)	Dal (from Jessore& Chittagong)
Beef	Fish (Cox's Bazar)
Mutton	Broiler Chicken (from Chittagong)
	Edible Oil (from Chittagong)
	Flour (from Chittagong)
	Tea (from Chittagong)
	Salt (from Chittagong)
	Sugar (from Chittagong)
	Bottled Water & Soft Drinks (from Chittagong)

* partly

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Accommodation Sector: Hotel purchase soap, toilet tissues, detergents, bulbs, furniture, construction materials etc. All these items are brought from Chittagong. Only to make wooden cottages wood and bamboo are collected from hilly forests of Bandarban.

Transportation Sector: Fuel for transports is purchased from the Fuel Stations in different points of Bandarban established by private enterprises.

Handicraft Sector: Raw materials for handicrafts are collected mostly from local sources. Only wool and thread are brought from Chittagong.

Tourism Investment Climate

Tourism Investment Climate in Bandarban is not favorable to the investors at all. Investing in tourism sector is challenged with so many legal and economic constraints for the local investors and the investors from outside Bandarban district, let alone foreign investors.

Local Investment: Local investors refer to those investors who are citizen/permanent residents of Bandarban Hill District. The basic constraint for local people is they are having no or quite inadequate capital and business knowledge for establishing a tourism business. They have land, but they have no capital to invest. The state owned bank Sonali Bank and Bangladesh Agricultural Bank offer Agricultural Loan to the local farmers (Maximum 30,000 taka, with 5% interest rate for tribal people and 14% for Bengali). Banks do not offer loan for tourism sector in Bandarban. It is surprising that excepting Sonali Bank and Agricultural Bank, only three private banks are having small offices in the district town. The following table shows the names of the banks :

Banks in Bandarban
Sonali Bank Ltd. Bangladesh Agricultural Bank Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd., Trust Bank Ltd., and BRAC Bank Ltd.

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd., Trust Bank Ltd., and BRAC Bank Ltd. have their branch in Bandarban with limited service. They do not offer any SME/tourism loan.

Investment from outside: Investors from outside Bandarban face great challenge for land ownership. Though they have money and business knowledge, they are not allowed to purchase land freely. Unfortunately taking lease of land or transfer in any form is not allowed without the prior permission of BDHC as per provision of CHT accord of 1997. It acts as great deterrent for investment from outside.

Current Challenges in Service Supply

Accommodation and Restaurant Sector: Hotels and restaurants in Bandarban face some common challenges regarding utility supplies, and some of the more specific challenges are specified in bullet points:

Shortage in water supply: In Bandarban Sadar, water is supplied by the Public Health department from Sangu river water purification plant. But the water supply is not enough to fulfill demand, specifically in dry season when the need for water increases due to tourist season, supply of water goes low due to low water flow in Sangu in winter.

Shortage in electricity supply: Load shedding is very common in Bandarban for hours after hours.

No gas: As there is no gas in Bandarban, restaurants cook food using wood, which is expensive.

Transportation Sector: Transports, mainly road transports are facing one major problem with poor condition of roads, especially during the rainy season they have to close their operation in certain routes.

Handicraft Sector: Seasonality of demand was identified as one main problem by the craftsmen. Handicrafts are sold only in peak tourist season, and during off-peak season sales are almost zero as tourists are the main customers of handicrafts. So that craftsmen do not take it as their occupation as it is not consistent in term of demand and sale. So that, even in peak tourist season when factories want to employ some seasonal craftsmen to meet increased demand, they do not find craftsmen. This time they attempt to collect handicrafts from craft villages. Again transportation is another problem. Most of the handicraft shops cannot collect product from remote craft villages as the roads are not good to bring them from remote areas where individual craftsman makes handicrafts at home. Another problem in this sector is increase in price of raw materials specifically wool and thread.

Supply Growth Trends and Potential

The number of hotel, restaurant and transportation in Bandarban is increasing and it will continue to increase in future. Though any reliable historical data is not available it is certain that the supply sector is growing at a high growth rate as more and more people find it profitable.

Number of hotels in Bandarban Sadar has been increasing rapidly for the last few years. As mentioned earlier, the number of hotel in Bandarban Sadar in 2013 is 42, whereas it was only 30 in 2010. Number of restaurants is also increasing. Though most of the restaurants know nothing about quality standard and law, recently some good restaurants (Ruposhi Bangla Restaurant, Zaman Restaurant and Biryani House etc.) have been established to serve upper class tourists. From this, we can guess that upper class tourists are getting interested to visit Bandarban.

Though the number of local bus will not increase that operate in different routes in Bandarban, the number of jeep and CNG auto rickshaw will continue to increase.

Handicraft shops are the only exception due to the marketing constraints, as stated by the President of Bandarban Woman Chamber of Commerce and Industry. But still the number of handicraft shops is increasing.

Tourism Demand of Bandarban

Tourism Source Market

Nationality: Tourists visiting Bandarban are mainly domestic tourists. Tourists mainly from Dhaka, Chittagong, Narayanganj and other districts come to Bandarban for adventure tourism. In 2011, 1036 foreign tourist sand in 2012, 1205 foreign tourists came (Afroz&Hasanuzzaman, 2012). But, they are for official or business purpose (working for foreign NGOs and UNDP).

Seasonal and Growth Trends: Winter is the peak tourism season for Bandarban. From October to March tourists visit Bandarban mostly. Especially after two Eids (Eid-ul-Fitre and Eid-ul-Azha: two major religious festivals of Muslim community), people get their holiday visit to Bandarban to enjoy their holidays. Though there has been no specific data and statistics on total number of tourists visiting Bandarban, but from our field survey it has been estimated that around 7 hundred thousand tourists visit Bandarban each year.

Length of Stay: Length of stay by the tourists indicates the specific market segment for Bandarban tourism. As per the hoteliers and other tourism stakeholders, three major types of tourists come to Bandarban: first, the who covers both Bandarban and Cox’s Bazar stay in bandarban as transit tourist. Secondly, the tourists who come for rest, relaxation, and recreation and sight-seeing. Their over-night stay is a bit more than the transit tourists. And lastly, the adventure tourists who come with a motivation to explore Bandarban, penetrate into remote areas of the hilly district, love trekking and hiking. Consequently their stay is much longer than any other tourist type. The following table shows average night stay by the tourists at Bandarban.

1 night	26%
2-3 nights	37%
4-7 nights	37%

Figure 5.1: Length of stay in Bandarban

Daily Expenditure: Daily expenditure of a tourist has roughly been estimated at an average of 1550 taka and the break-down is as follows:

Expenditure Heads	Amount in BDT	Percentage (%)
1. Accommodation	300	19
2. Food	450	29
3. Transport (local)	400	26
4. Buying local products (handicrafts)	200	13
5. Others	200	13
Total	1550	100

Figure 5.2: Daily expenditure of a tourist in percentage.

Market Segmentation

Motivation: To analyze the motivation for visiting Bandarban, tourists were asked to fill questionnaire and rate the importance of the factors based on five-point Likert scale. In our 5 points Likert Scale, we imposed the value ranging from 1 to 5 representing ‘Strongly Disagree’ to ‘Strongly Agree’ respectively.

Six motivation factors were given to rank among them to the tourists. The following ranking was found from the mean value of each motivation factor. (See Annex)

Ranking	Motivation Factor	Mean
1	For seeing the hills and forest	4.69
2	For enjoying the natural environment	4.62
3	For adventure activities	4.48
4	For sensing peace and quiet	4.46
5	For knowing local/ethnic culture	4.04
6	For spending time with family/friends	2.60

From the table it becomes quite clear that seeing the hills and forests is the number one motivation of the tourists followed by natural beauty, adventure, relax and recreation, and knowing the tribal people.

Purpose: The purpose of visiting Bandarban is basically adventure. 70% of the tourists visit Bandarban for adventure; followed by leisure, recreation and holiday (26%) and visiting friends and relatives or VFR (4%).

Adventure	70%
Leisure, recreation and holiday	26%
VFR	4%

Tourists in VFR category are basically Bengali tourists visiting their tribal friends who study or work in Dhaka or Chittagong with them.

Market Flows

Routes Markets take to enter/exit Bandarban: Tourists enter Bandarban mostly from Dhaka and Chittagong and return to their home after visiting Bandarban as they come to visit only Bandarban and don't want to visit any other neighboring destination. But some tourists come to Bandarban as part of a circuitous tour. These tourists may go to Cox's Bazar after visiting Bandarban. We can estimate the percentage of both type tourists from survey questionnaire.

Tourist visiting Bandarban only	74%
Circuitous tour (Home – Bandarban – Cox's Bazar – Home)	26%

Type of Transportation used: Most of the tourists (93%) use bus to come from their home district to Bandarban. Rests of the 7% tourists use both rail and bus.

Bus	93%
Both Rail and Bus	7%

Market Growth Trends and Potentials

Undeniably, the number of tourists is increasing rapidly and this will continue in future. We can guess the growth rate in tourist flow from the rapid growth of tourism supply sectors including hotel, restaurant, and transport.

Though tourists are not fully satisfied with accommodation and transportation system in Bandarban, they want to revisit Bandarban and also will recommend it to other to visit. 60% of the tourists are satisfied with accommodation facilities in Bandarban, whereas, only 33% tourists are satisfied with transports. But, all the tourists (100%) want to revisit Bandarban, whereas, 96% tourists will recommend others to visit Bandarban.

Tourism development is expected in Bandarban for the greater benefit of the local people- both the ethnic and non-ethnic. But it must be in a sustainable way without hampering the nature of this paradise and unique culture of the ethnic people and for their long-term economic benefit.

As it was said by the late king as follows-

“We welcome guests, but don't want Bandarban to become crowded or polluted like Rangamati. We don't want to lose our culture nor see it consigned to a museum. ”

—Raja AungShuePrueChowdhury

Bandarban Tourism Treasure and SWOT Analysis

Vast tourism treasure of Bandarban has yet to be explored. The exploration of this treasure must be done in some planned way. Otherwise, unnecessary making of pucca roads, making bridges and culverts, concrete building structures, huge influx of tourists etc. may spoil the ecology and environment of the district. Today or tomorrow it will be one of the paradises for eco-tourism and the adventure lovers who will find the meaning of life in roaming around in the natural wilderness of this hilly district. We have tried to identify the SWOT elements of this majestic paradise. The followings are the notable SWOT elements of Bandarban:

SWOT analysis of tourism in Bandarban

Strength	Weakness	Opportunity	Threat
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the most <i>exotic unspoilt</i> tourist attractions in Bangladesh, combining natural and cultural aspects • The four highest peaks of Bangladesh are located in Bandarban district • Raikhiang Lake, the highest lake in Bangladesh, as well as the picturesque 2000 years old Boga lake, believed to be the crater of a volcano, are situated in Bandarban • Well connected by roads from Dhaka (6-7 hours journey by bus), Chittagong (2 hours) and Cox's 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No clear tourism responsibilities • Could not create image as unparalleled destination, as there has not been enough promotional efforts and a clear brand has not been developed. • Seasonal tourism trend • Scattered tourism development with no planning • Scarcity of electricity and water supply • Poor service standard in accommodation in Bandarban Sadar • Below standard rest houses/ tin-shed cottage having no 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential market for Bandarban is increasing as domestic tourism is flourishing at a jumping pace in Bangladesh. • Responsibilities for local tourism (now on national level) will be delegated to the district level in CHT. • Many attractive sites of Bandarban are yet to be explored • Concept of trekking and track tourism is getting popularity and Bandarban will be the heaven for hill trekking For example: "Hiking" is getting popular among young tourists of Bangladesh, after 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Threat for ecological imbalance - including flora and fauna, forest and river - due to the probable erection of unplanned tourism super structure and infrastructure. • No attempt to calculate TCC (tourist carrying capacity). Otherwise huge influx of tourists may destroy the environmental and ecological balances. • Potential risk of misconception about tourism in local communities. • Potential conflict between tourists and local

<p>Bazar (3 hours)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exotic trekking trails through virgin forests and chance to meet more than 11 tribes of the region • Tremendous opportunity for introducing track tourism (sight-seeing blended with a bit of adventurous flavor), rest, relax, and recreation tourism. • The highest number of ethnic minorities living in the district beside the Bengalis • Law and order situation in Bandarban is considered the best in the country. • Bandarban is a land of “one destination with hundreds of diverse tourism activities” – the type rarely found in Bangladesh. Tourism-friendly and proactive district administration (DC’s office, BHDC, Bandarban Police etc.) is working for developing tourism in the district and promoting it. 	<p>good facility for sleeping and wash room in trekking routes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor condition of remote internal roads (Ruma to Boga Lake for example) • Old fashioned and uncomfortable vehicles (public transport as well as vehicles for private rent) operating in different routes not ideal for the tourists. • Poor quality of food, hygiene, standard of restaurant, and food services • Lack of trained and experienced tour guides for trekking, lack of association and pricing guidelines • Unfavorable investment climate, e.g. long business permit processes, outsiders cannot buy land in the hilly district • No formal tourism business associations to ensure coordinated tourism development • No formal plan for involving the local 	<p>conquering the Mt. Everest by Bangladeshis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People of plain land have strong interest to visit hilly lands and sea, as such diverse landscapes are attractive to them. Bandarban is situated in such a strategic point where people can combine a visit to the hills with the Bay of Bengal just in 3 hours time. • Establishing more eco-friendly resorts on the hills with good facilities can create huge demand for the wealthy sunlust tourists • Opportunity for rearing up handicrafts for uniqueness and ethnic design • Attractive colorful cultural performances by different ethnic groups which are not common in other parts of the country. • Tribal lifestyle of remote hills is attracts the interest of plain land people. Land of “one destination with hundreds of tourism 	<p>community for misbehavior by one of them or by both of them.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential conflict between tribal community and outsider investors in tourism business as local communities might have a fear for loss of control over their economy. • Having neighboring competitors offering similar tourism products (Rangamati and KhagraChhari) • Fear of terrorism and abduction in the minds of the tourists which may act as a deterrent factor for tourism development. • People and the government appear to have limited awareness of the benefits of tourism
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	ethnic community with tourism. Dhaka based tour operators are more interested for operating tours in Cox's Bazar, Saint Martin's island, the Sundarbans, as these are popular destinations.	activities" – the type rarely found in Bangladesh.	
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From the SWOT analysis it is evident that Bandarban has strong potential to develop as a flourishing tourism destination. Though a number of challenges, such as the lack of proper planning, limited quality accommodation services in the urban hub as well as in the remote destinations for trekking, , absence of good transport system etc. are affecting tourism sector of Bandarban, huge potential for future development is there. Sustainable tourism development and institutional innovations, improved collaboration among stakeholders, and community engagement in tourism can improve the livelihood of the local community people across Bandarban.

Tourism Context of Ruma Sub- district

Chapter 6

A Case Study on Ruma Sub-district

Ruma is an Upazila of Bandarban District in the Division of Chittagong, Bangladesh. Ruma Upazila (Bandarban district) with an area of 492.10 km square is bordered by Rowangchhari upazila in northern, southern Thanchi, Belaichhari upazila on the east and Bandarban Sadar upazilas on the west llama. Main river is Sangu (Shankha). Ruma (Town) consists Mouza. The city area is km 33.67sq. As of the 2011 Bangladesh census, Ruma has a population of 29098. There are 15469 male & 13629 female. Literacy rate among the town people is 44.4%.

Ruma is located at 22.0500°N 92.4167°E. It has 5917 units of household. Males constitute are 53.16% of the population, and females 46.83%. This Upazila's eighteen up population is 10144. Ruma has an average literacy rate of 27.8% (7+ years), and the national average of 32.4% literate.

Ruma has 4 Unions/Wards, 14 Mauzas/Mahallas, and 155 villages.

Figure 6.1: Maps of Ruma Sub-district

Source:

1. *Banglapedia, The National Encyclopedia of Bangladesh*
2. *Bangladesh Population Census 2011, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics*
3. <http://chittagong.com>

Situation Analysis of Ruma:

Demographics and Poverty:

Distribution of Population:

There are 29098 people living in Ruma. Ruma has a wide variety in tribal group. There are four union parishod at Ruma. The most populous union is Ruma Union the least populous is RemakriPransa Union.

Poverty Mapping across the Sub-district:

37-55% people of Ruma live below the poverty line. The reason behind this economic condition is the lack of the opportunity of economic activity. Most of the people live on jumm cultivation, and the infrastructural facility is very bad. The farmers do not get fair price of their produces because of almost impassable roads and communication system. Middlemen purchase the crops from the farmers at a very low price.

There is no available information on the poverty mapping of Ruma Sub-district according to unions. But the whole sub-district is a poverty stricken region.

Ethnic Diversity and Spread:

There are 26503 ethnic minority people living in Ruma. The following table shows the ethnic distribution in Ruma.

Table 6.1: Ethnic minority in different Union Parishod of Ruma

Name of the Union Parishod	Bengali	Ethnic minority/Tribal people					Total Population
		Marma	Mro	Tripura	Others	Total Ethnic minority/Tribal	
Paindu	662	3402	4	0	2301	5707	6369
RemakriPransa	543	70	1278	1447	2355	5150	5639
Ruma Union	968	5066	719	714	3609	10108	11076
Ghalangya	422	1060	3363	841	274	5538	5960
Total	2595	9598	5364	3002	8539	26503	29098

Source : BBS. Bangladesh Population Census 2011.

Figure 6.2: The distribution of ethnic people is presented in the diagram below:

Main economic sector:

Main sectors & industries across the district:

There is no specific survey on the main sectors and industries of Ruma. As per our survey we have found that the main economic activity is joom cultivation. Besides some people are involved with wood business, and now some other are involving with the tourism industry, a few people are involved with handicraft production and selling.

Main Distribution Market:

Ruma plays the leadership role in distributing the product produced in this area. There are other two minor markets in this Sub-district, RemakriPransa and Ghalangya.

Chapter 7

Tourism Attractions of Ruma

Key Tourist Attractions:

There are a number of tourist attractions in Ruma. Some of these are presented below with brief descriptions:

Figure 7.1: Location of Tourist Attractions in Ruma Sub-district

1. Boga Lake

One of the most beautiful natural lake in Bangladesh. It is the second highest lake in Bangladesh. This lake is a reservoir of water created by rounded hill around it. Geologists are of the opinion that Bogalake was a crater of a volcano which might have erupted sometime in the past. It is located in the RemakriPransha Union in Ruma. At the afternoon it gives a panoramic view with the reflection of light.

2.Mt. keokradong

Officially it is called the second highest peak of Bangladesh, though some other peaks have been identified which are higher than the Keokradong. Keokradong is visited by a number of tourists during winter season. Recently some local accommodation facility has been developed on Keokradong. It is in the same trail of Boga lake. One can feel the wide view of other hills from here.

3. Mt. Tazingdong

Officially the highest peak of Bangladesh is the Tazingdong. Huge number of trekkers trek every year to Tazingdong to have their feet on Tazingding. It is also called as Bijoy (victory).

4. Rijhuk Waterfall

This waterfall is very close to Ruma. One can go to this waterfall by boat. It will take only 30 minutes to go to the waterfall. It is directly falling onto the Sangu river. One also will be able to enjoy the panoramic view of Sangu during the journey.

5. JadiPhai Waterfall

Jadiphai is one of the most beautiful waterfalls in Bangladesh. It is different from other waterfalls because of its width. The waterfall creates a smoky atmosphere in the area. Crystal clear water and the stony body have given it the most attractive look.

6. Raikkhong Lake:

The highest and the longest hilly natural lake is the Raikkhong Lake. It is actually located at the Belaichharisubdistrict of Rangamati. But if anyone want to go to Raikkhonglake s/he has to go through Ruma. For this reason we have considered this as the attraction of Ruma. This is called the most beautiful lake in Bangladesh. During rainy season cloud gives it a fantastic view. There is a Tripura para beside the lake. This lake is also called as the PUKUR PARA lake.

7. RaikkhongMukh

It is very closer to the Raikkhonglake. The whole canal is very beautiful. Someone can enjoy new beauty with each and every extra miles. People of the tribal village named Prongjangpara are very much hospitable. This is a Tripura Para. Staying at this tribal village makes the trekking more enjoyable. This is also located at Belaichhorisubdistrict of Rangamati. But the only way to go there is through Ruma. For this reason we have considered it as the attraction of Ruma.

8. Shrimp Waterfall/ChingriJhiri

This beautiful small waterfall is located on the trail from Boga Lake to Keokradong. It takes 90 minutes on an average to reach ChingriJhiri. During the rainy season it take a beautiful look. Those who trek to Keokradong can easily cover ChingriJhiri.

9. Balkai Waterfall

This is another most attractive waterfall situated at Ruma. The water flows from high altitude in monsoon. The trekking route is very risky and only the ultimate adventurous trekkers brave to reach to the waterfall.

10. Double Falls

This waterfall is unique from the view point that it has two divided falls from one waterfall. It is located near Rumana Para. Though only a few number of courageous people visit the fall but it is expected that the arrival will rise day by day. If anyone wants to stay at the waterfall s/he can do it as there is plain land beside the waterfall where one can set his/her tent to stay.

11. Lifestyle

Lifestyle of the tribal people of Ruma is also a great attraction of Ruma. The life-style and livelihood pattern of the tribal people are totally different. Life-style of different tribal groups also notably differ from each others' life-style.

Photo Credit:

Md. Mehedi Hasan, Department of Tourism & Hospitality Management, University of Dhaka.
<http://ashavabik.blogspot.com>.

Serajul Mustakim Peal, Extreme Travellers.

Waci Ahmed, Department of Tourism & Hospitality Management, University of Dhaka.

Banglatrek.org

Chapter 8

Structure of the tourism industry in Ruma

Review of Accommodation in Ruma

Ruma is very popular for some unique natural attractions like Boga Lake, Rijuk Water Fall, Darjiling Para, Keokradong Hill, Passim Para, ZadiPhai Fall, Double Fall, Jingsium Fall, and Tajing Dong Hill. But hotels are concentrated in Ruma Bazar (Market) area as it is a transit point and tourists prefer to stay here and take a trip from this point to these places. Some other cottages are being operated in Boga Lake and Keokradong those cannot be termed as hotel, offering overnight stay and food service.

Type of Accommodation: Hotel and cottage are the main form of accommodation in Ruma.

Number of Accommodation: In Ruma Bazar, there are 8 hotels and 6 cottages in Boga Lake and 1 cottage in Keokradong.

Areas	No. of hoteland cottage	Total No. of Beds
Hotels in Ruma Bazar	8 hotels	200-250
Cottages in Boga Lake	6 cottages	180-200
Cottage in Keokradong	1 cottage	30-40
Total	15	410-490

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Hotels are very small in size in Ruma Bazar and with very limited facility. Some of them do not offer separate bathroom for each room, rather guests have to share some common bathrooms. Though total bed capacity of the hotels in Ruma Bazar is around 200-250 altogether, they manage to accommodate around 500 tourists each night during peak season especially after two Eids. It has been only possible as tourists, especially students, share beds; and even 5 of them spend night on a double bed.

The cottages in Boga Lake and Keokradong are also small in size. But they can accommodate more tourists, as there is no provision for separate bed and guests have to sleep on floor. The cottages are made of wood and corrugated sheets (tin). There is no wash room attached. Very bad shaped so-called toilet is situated far away from the cottages and it becomes difficult for the city people to use the toilets.

Price Range: Like Bandarban Sadar, price range can be categorized according the type of accommodation in Ruma. Though there is no class hotel in Ruma at all, but category can be done.

Hotel	Cheap: BDT 100-200 Normal: BDT 500-1000 Standard: BDT 1000-1600
Cottage	BDT 100- 200 per bed for one night

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Occupancy throughout the year: As tourism is seasonal in pattern in Bandarban, occupancy rate is also not the same throughout the year in Ruma also. During peak tourism season from October to March the average occupancy rate is 40%-50% on an average whereas during the off-peak season the occupancy rate is between 10% and 15% in Ruma Bazar area. But the scenario is little different in the cottages in Boga Lake and Keokradong. In peak tourism season the occupancy rate is around 60% but during off-peak season the rate is 0%.

<i>Area</i>	Occupancy Rate (%)	
	<i>Peak season (Oct to March)</i>	<i>Off-Peak season</i>
Ruma Bazar	40%-50%	10%-15%
Boga Lake	60%-100%	0%-10%
Keokradong	40%-60%	0%-10%

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

These hotels and cottages are used only by the tourists in tourist season and no local people use these as they don't need to stay overnight at hotel in Ruma at all.

Review of Food and Beverage Facilities in Ruma

In Ruma Bazar there are 6 restaurants offering heavy food item (rice) for lunch and dinner. These are quite similar to the restaurants operating in Bandarban Sadar. In Boga Lake 6 cottage owners offer food service to their guests who are staying in their cottage. At Keokradong too there is provision for food arranged by the cottage owner only.

	<i>No. of Restaurant</i>
Ruma Bazar	6
Boga Lake	6 (cottage)
Keokradong	1 (cottage)

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Type of food served: Restaurants operating in Ruma Bazar offer fishcurry, chicken curry, muttoncurry, beefcurry, and vegetables for lunch and dinner. They offer Ruti, Porota, egg, vegetable, soup, and tea for breakfast. Biryani is not served in these restaurants.

In the cottage restaurants in Boga Lake and Keokradong similar type of food is served. But, sometimes they arrange some exclusive tribal food if requested by the guests.

Price range: For lunch or dinner in any restaurant in Ruma Bazar with three course (vegetable + chicken/fish/beef + dal) one will be charged BDT 80-120. For the same meal one will be charged BDT 100-150 for the food service provided by the cottages in Boga Lake and Keokradong.

Review of Tour Agencies and Guides in Ruma

In Ruma, tourists must seek permission from the Police or the Army or the BGB check-point when they are to go for trekking from Boga Lake to Keokradong and beyond. At the time of entry they must have a local tour guide, otherwise they won't be allowed for trekking. There are three tour guide association in Ruma.

Name of the Guide Association	Number of Guides
PothProdorshok Tour Guide	42
You & Me Tours	28

Source: Field Survey, 2013.

Rate: They charge on per person basis for Ruma to Keokradong trekking route, but for other trekking routes they make contract with a tourist group consisting not more than 20 tourists. They charge for their service according the chart fixed by the local authority (Sub-district council).

Trekking Route	Rate in BDT
Ruma – Keokradong Peak	500 (per person)
Ruma – Thanchi	5000 (per group)
Ruma – ZadiPhai Water Fall	2500 (,,)
Ruma – Raikkhong Lake(Rangamati)	5000 (,,)
Ruma – Sungsung Para – Rumana Para Waterfall	4000 (,,)

Source: You & Me Tours.Ruma

Review of Transportation in Ruma

Jeep (ChanderGari) and Engine Boat are the main types of local transport in Ruma. Though scheduled buses are operated regularly between Bandarban Sadar and Ruma, bus is not operated in any route within the Ruma Sub-district as roads are not good for bus. Jeep is the most suitable transport in Ruma, but during the rainy season it also becomes risky as the roads are not good.

Engine Boat: In Ruma there are total 24 engine boats operating in different routes in the Sangu river under two Owner's Associations, namely "Speed Boat Owners' Association of Ruma" (Association of Bengali boat owners), and "Sangu Speed Boat Owners' Association" (Association of tribal boat owners)⁸.

Rate: Rate for different routes is fixed by the local authority.

Route	Rate
Ruma Bridge – Ruma Bazar	BDT 30 (per person)
Ruma–Bandarban Sadar	BDT 100 (per person)/ BDT 3500 (reserve boat)
Ruma- Thanchi	BDT 5000 (reserve boat)
BandarbanSadar- Thanchi	BDT 7000 (reserve boat)
Ruma–Rijuk Water Fall	BDT 1500 (reserve boat)

Source: "Speed Boat Owners' Association of Ruma", and "Sangu Speed Boat Owners' Association".

⁸"Speed Boat Owners' Association of Ruma," and "Sangu Speed Boat Owners' Association"

Each of the boats can carry 10 passengers on an average; so the total seat is 240 altogether for boat passengers including local people and tourists. Total number of people working in these boats including boatman, helper, and line-man is around 100. (Source: “Speed Boat Owners’ Association of Ruma”, and “Sangu Speed Boat Owners’ Association”.)

Jeep (ChanderGari): In Ruma, the number of ChanderGari (Jeep) is 20 and there are other 5 micro-buses (Land-cruiser and Nissan Patrol) operated in different routes within Ruma. All these cars are owned by 12 owners and operated under the same owner’s association namely, ‘Ruma Jeep-Car Owners’ Association’.

Type of Car	No. of Vehicles	No. of Seats(each car)	Total sitting capacity
ChanderGari	20	14	280
Micro-bus	5	8	40
Total	25		320

Source: Ruma Jeep-Car Owners’ Association.

These cars are operated on contract basis, that is, the whole car is to be hired for a trip to a certain spot or spots, and it may also be up-down trip for a certain rate fixed by the local authority.

Rate: The rate for different spots is fixed by the local authority.

Some of the jeep routes and rates in Ruma are⁹:

Route	Rate in BDT (for whole car)	
	Single trip*	Up-down trip**
Ruma – Boga Lake	2,000	4,000
Ruma – Boga Lake – Keokradong	6,000	8,000
Ruma –Theikhiang Para	10,000	15,000
Ruma –Moonwam Para	2000	4000

*Trip from one point to another point with no returning trip** Trip from one point to another and returning from destination point to departing point

Total number of people working in these cars including driver, helper, and line-man is around 60. This number will increase in future as the number of cars is increasing every year. Though tourists visit and use these transports in winter, local people use them round the

⁹Ruma Jeep-Car Owners’ Association

year. Popularity and use of these cars are increasing among tourists and local people as the best mode of transport in Ruma.

Review of Handicraft shops in Ruma

In Ruma, there are only two handicraft shops in Ruma Bazar area. One is ‘Anny Store’ and another one is ‘Bawm Zung’. Both of them are run by tribal craftsmen on sole proprietorship basis. They make and sell all tribal textile, woollen, and wooden products as described in the part of Bandarban. Though they make these products by themselves, but during the peak tourism season they collect handicrafts from nearby ‘Para’ or village to meet the demand.

In Ruma, different types of handicrafts are made by different tribal groups. But, they cannot take it as their profession as the demand for these products is seasonal and they can sell them only when tourists come to their village during peak tourism season. So that, they do not make these for commercial purpose; rather they make these for their traditional and own use.

Backward Linkage of the Tourism Industry

As Ruma is a sub-district of Bandarban, the pattern of backward linkage is same to that of Bandarban. The only difference is, input supplies brought from Chittagong, Jessore, and Cox’s Bazar are brought to Ruma via Bandarban Sadar.

Figure8.1: Materials supply flow to Ruma

Current Challenges in Service Supply

Accommodation and Restaurant Sector: Hotels and restaurants in Ruma face more challenges than those in Bandarban Sadar regarding utility supplies, and some different others:

Shortage in water supply: In Ruma Bazar, water is supplied using Gravity Flow System (GFS) from nearby water falls. But the water supply is not enough to fulfil demand, specifically in dry season when the water falls get weak but the need for water increases due to tourist season.

Shortage in electricity supply: Load shedding condition is worse in Ruma than it is in Bandarban.

No gas: There is no provision for gas in Ruma. So naturally people have to depend on woods for cooking and other household purposes.

Poor Transportation System: Tourists, especially those in a family tour, don't show interest to visit Ruma as transportation system is poor in Ruma. They visit Bandarban Sadar only and then go back to their home.

Transportation Sector: Transports, mainly road transports are facing one major problem with poor condition of roads, especially during the rainy season they have to close their operation in Ruma.

Handicraft Sector: Craftsmen in Ruma face the same problems as described in Bandarban section.

Supply Growth Trends and Potential

Ruma is gaining popularity among the domestic tourists day by day. The number of tourists is increasing every year. Newer and newer spots are being explored every year, for example,

The number of jeeps is increasing every year to meet the demand of increased number of tourists, and the following table is showing the actual growth trend.¹⁰

Year	2010	2011	2012	2013
No. of Jeeps	14	18	20	25

But hotels in Ruma Bazar area are facing a new challenge. Ruma Bazar itself is not a tourist attraction, rather it a transit point between Bandarban Sadar and Boga Lake to beyond. Earlier, as it was not possible to reach Boga Lake in a single day, tourists had to stay

¹⁰Ruma Jeep-Car Owners' Association

overnight in Ruma Bazar. But recently the 'Ruma Bridge' has been opened for public use that connects Bandarban by road to Ruma. So that tourists can go directly to Boga Lake from Bandarban Sadar without taking any break in Ruma. Consequently, the occupancy rate in Ruma is decreasing day by day but it is increasing in Boga Lake and Keokradong on the other hand.

Tourism Demand of Ruma

Tourism Source Market

Nationality: Bangladeshi tourists are the main source market of Ruma. Foreign tourists visiting Ruma are very insignificant in number and most of them are for official or business purpose. The number of tourists visiting Ruma is approximately 8,000 to 10,000 yearly.¹¹

Seasonal and Growth Trends: Tourism is seasonal in Ruma. During the winter season from October to March in every weekend 50- 60 tourists visit Ruma. After each Eid around 1500 tourists visit Ruma in 10 days¹². In rainy season it is tough to visit Ruma as road transports are shut during this period. But the number of tourists in Ruma is increasing due to the development of road to different spots like Boga Lake and Keokradong.

Length of Stay: From the survey questionnaire analysis, it is found that most of the tourists (82%) stay 2-3 nights in Ruma and rest of the 18% tourists stay 1 night.

2-3 nights	82%
1 night	18%

Daily Expenditure: Daily expenditure of a tourist is roughly estimated on an average 1350 taka.

Expenditure Heads	Amount in BDT	Percentage (%)
1. Accommodation	300	22
2. Food	250	18
3. Transport (local)	400	30
4. Buying local products (handicrafts)	200	15
5. Others	200	15
Total	1350	100

Source: Tourist Survey, 2013.

¹¹ Ruma Police Check-point

¹² Ruma Police Check-point

Market Segmentation (Motivation for travel):

Motivation: Tourists motivation for visiting Ruma was analyzed by asking tourist rate the importance of the factors based on five-point Likert scale. In our 5 points Likert Scale, we imposed the value ranging from 1 to 5 representing 'Strongly Disagree' to 'Strongly Agree' respectively. Data was analyzed by using SPSS 11.5 for Windows.

Six motivation factors were given to rank among them to the tourists. The following ranking was found from the mean value of each motivation factor.

Ranking	Motivation Factor	Mean
1	For seeing the hills and forest	4.81
2	For enjoying the natural environment	4.50
3	For adventure activities	4.36
4	For sensing peace and quiet	4.30
5	For knowing local/ethnic culture	3.64
6	For spending time with family/friends	2.33

Like Bandarban, hills and forests, coming closer to nature, adventure recreation and rest, and ethnic culture are the main motivation factors.

Purpose: Tourists visit Ruma basically for adventure. 91% of the tourists surveyed were visiting for adventure coupled with enjoying hills and hilly life; and rest 9% were visiting friends and relatives (VFR).

Adventure	91%
VFR	9%

It should be mentioned that, tourists in VFR category are basically Bengali tourists visiting their tribal friends who study or work in Dhaka or Chittagong with them.

Market Flows

Tourists enter Ruma mainly from Bandarban Sadar and exit in the same way after visiting spots in Ruma. But some adventurers go to Thanchi by trekking from Boga Lake and Keokradong. They go to Thanchi sub-district and then go to Bandarban Sadar directly from Thanchi. Tourists mainly use jeep and engine boat as mode of transport in Ruma.

Market Growth Trends and Potentials

Though the major market of Ruma is consist of students of colleges and universities of different districts of Bangladesh, other type of tourists will also visit Ruma if service and facilities required by these classes can be ensured. Though the present condition of tourist facility and infrastructure is not good, if properly financed and promoted it will be another tourist capital of Bangladesh.

Though 82% touristssurveyed in Ruma are not satisfied with accommodation in Ruma, and 55% tourists are dissatisfied with transportation, but 100% of the tourists want to revisit Ruma and 91% tourists will recommend the name of Ruma to others to visit it. Ruma is going to be the hot spot for adventure tourism in near future.

SWOT analysis of tourism in Ruma

Ruma is famous for its scenic beauty with so many trekking trails, mountains, waterfalls, river and forests. Ruma is abundant with tribal diversity. Total 15 ethnic groups live in Ruma, which is the highest number of ethnic group living together in a sub-district. The following is the SWOT analysis for Ruma:

Strength	Weakness	Opportunity	Threat
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy accessible from Dhaka via Bandarban • Rich with so many trekking trails, mountains, waterfalls, and forests that make it one of the ideal most places for hill trekking and adventure tourism in Bangladesh • Two of the four highest peaks of Bangladesh - Tahjindong and Keokradong - are located in Ruma sub-district • Mysterious Boga Lake, the most popular natural lake in Bangladesh and the icon of Bandarban, is located in Ruma. It is about 2000fts above sea level & 17km away from Ruma Bazar. • Abundant with so many famous 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A good number of competitive destinations are in existence in other adjacent sub-districts offering the same tourism products • Trekking is more popular in winter, tourists cannot trek in remote areas of Ruma during rainy season due to bad weather and restriction imposed by local authority • Scarcity of electricity and water supply is more acute in Ruma than it is in Bandarban. • Poor condition of accommodation facility in Ruma Bazar. • Below standard rest houses/ tin-shed cottage having no good facility for sleeping and wash room in trekking routes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concept of trekking and track tourism is getting popularity. • Keokradong and Tahjindong have been established as traditional site for hill trekking in Ruma • Market demand for Ruma (as well as Bandarban) is increasing and it will continue to increase • Opportunity for nurturing handicrafts with uniqueness and ethnic design • Potential for establishing locally produced organic food and setting up small processing plants for pineapples, mango orange. • Varied tribal lifestyle and culture could be turned into tourist product. • Tourism is being accepted as a good 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having neighboring competitors (specially Thanchi) offering almost same tourism products • Threat for ecological balance - including flora and fauna, forest and river - due to the probable erection of unplanned tourism super structure and infrastructure. • No attempt to calculate TCC (tourist carrying capacity). Otherwise huge influx of tourists may destroy the environmental and ecological balances. • Potential risk of misconception about tourism in local communities. • Potential conflict between tourists and local community for misbehavior by one of them or by both

<p>waterfalls of Bangladesh, like Rijuk waterfall, Zadiphai fall, Double fall, Jingsiam fall, Shrimp fall and many unknown others.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The popular most trekking trails in Bangladesh through hilly forests and tribal villages of Keokradong and Tahjingdong are located in Ruma • Ruma is bestowed with tribal diversity. 11 ethnic groups live in Ruma, which is the highest number of ethnic group living together in a sub-district. • Experiencing the tribal people, their life-style & culture, buy their own handicrafts, enjoying cultural shows, try ethnic cuisine, and stay overnight in tribal villages by the side of the trekking trails. • Sangu river – the wild daughter of Bandarban flows beside Ruma, thus making it important 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor Condition of Roads from Ruma to Boga Lake and beyond • Old fashioned and uncomfortable vehicles (buses, jeeps, and boats) operating in different routes • Poor quality food, low standard of restaurant, and food service • Lack of trained and experienced tour guides to lead tourists in hill trekking in Ruma • No formal tourism business association to work for tourism development in Ruma. • Though law and order situation is quite good but tourists sometimes are afraid of abduction, especially at the time of trekking in remote areas. • Unfavorable investment climate as outsiders cannot buy land in the hilly district • No formal plan for involving the local ethnic community with tourism. • After the 	<p>income source (from tour guiding, handicraft shops, cultural shows etc.) by the local ethnic groups</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BHDC and local administration are tourism-friendly and working for tourism development • Huge unexplored natural places, hills, waterfalls, other spots - if properly identified and tapped, Ruma could turn into an attractive destination for sunlust tourists too. • Introducing rafting through Sanguriver from Ruma can open up new avenue for tourism. 	<p>of them.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential conflict between tribal community and outsider investors in tourism business as local communities might have a fear for loss of control over their economy. • Fear of terrorism and abduction in the minds of the tourists which may act as a deterrent factor for tourism development.
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<p>backward and forward link market for trade & commerce, and tourism.</p>	<p>Rumabridge over Sangu has been completed, tourists can come to Ruma quickly by bus from Bandarban and therefore no need to overnight stay in Ruma. It hampers the business of the hoteliers.</p>		
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Chapter 9

Tourism Value Chain Analysis: Bandarban

Why people visit Bandarban? In several research works on Bandarban: as a tourist destination, it has been found that Bandarban is more popular for adventure type of tourism. Side by side Bandarban has been a good destination for the people who want to have a relaxed time amidst nature. However whatever is the motivation for tourism, the tourists need some basic facilities and services in the destination.

The tourism value chain in Bandarban generally integrates five main productive activities or sectors: accommodation, restaurants, transportation, handicrafts/shopping, and services like trekking, sightseeing etc.

Figure 9.1: Value Chain in tourism of Bandarban: Supply and Demand

The Overall tourism value chain in Bandarban

The tourism value chain in Bandarban generally integrates five main productive activities or sectors: accommodation, restaurants, transportation, handicrafts/shopping and tourism related services.

Figure9.2: Overall tourism Value Chain with identified actors and activities at Bandarban.

WHY PUT MORE IMPORTANCE ON TOURISM?

Unlike the plain land the CHT by virtue of its geographical configuration, inaccessibility, remote location from the main economic centres is having facilities for limited economic activities. The people have to depend on widespread Jhum farming. Agri-products are produced little and mostly used for self consumption of the hill people. Fruits (banana, pineapple, jackfruit, papaya), and spices (masala) like ginger, and turmeric are also produced in Bandarban. Recently many farmers have tilted towards cultivating more tobacco leaves; it being the main profitable cash crop. Bandarban does not have any significantly big or medium industry where people might have job opportunity.

However, this hilly district has such an important untapped resource which could be turned into most worthy and prodigious economic bolster. This is invariably the tourism sector. According to some rough estimation, tourism has become very important industry in Bandarban fetching more than 100 crore taka yearly. This will continue to grow as the domestic tourism in Bangladesh saw a big leap in recent years. Bandarban receives almost seven hundred thousands of tourists each year. If we can provide the tourists with better services, better access, and lengthen their stay in Bandarban, more tourist money will be retained in Bandarban which ultimately will benefit the local people. Consequently we propose to give much importance towards the development of tourism and hospitality sectors in Bandarban.

Analysis of the behavior (motivation) of tourists visiting Bandarban shows that almost 70% of the tourists come to this hilly district for adventure tourism, mainly trekking and track tourism (this is pathway tourism (walking or biking) following a specific circuitous route with less physical pains and exertions). 26% visit Bandarban for leisure, recreation, and holiday. These tourists could be good market segment for the 'track' tourism. They will recreate themselves, enjoy holidays and move around by walking or by cycling in the nearby areas of the resorts they stay (example could be 'Nilgiri' resort).

Keeping this behavioral pattern of the tourists in mind we have developed the following model where we try to show that what type of tourism is more potential for Bandarban, and also the areas where we have to put more emphasis in order to make tourism most rewarding to the people of Bandarban.

Figure 9.3:Types of Tourism and Relatively Important Facilities:
Model for Bandarban

—————> Most important and inseparable activities
 - - - - -> Less important optional activities

As most of the tourists visit Bandarban for adventure, it may be recommended that Bandarban should be branded as Adventure tourism ground. Side by side about one-fourth of the tourists visit Bandarban for rest, relax and recreation. For this segment of market some specific activities are more important; these are good accommodation, local cultural programs, shopping facility etc.

However, from the following two value chain analyses, we can see that in case of trekking tourism, although the tourists spend more nights in the district, out of total money spent by the trekkers almost 59% is retained outside Bandarban, remaining 41% directly goes to the local people. On the other hand, in case of sunlust tourism (rest, relax, recreation) almost 51% of tourist money remains inside Bandarban.

Table 9.1 : VALUE CHAIN MAP FOR RUMA TREKKING PACKAGE EXPENDITURE (2013)

Tourism Itinerary : Dhaka - Bandarban - Ruma - Boga Lake - Keokradang - Dhaka.

(Typical Package : 5 nights 4 days, Group of 6 persons)

Total Tourist Expenditure on Trekking Experience = Taka 14750 (per person)						
Published price of Travel and Trekking Package = Taka 14,000 (per person)						
Share of Tourist Expenditure						
Outside Bandarban = Taka 8750(59.32)			Cost of Inputs within Bandarban (including Ruma) = Taka 6000 (40.68%)			
Taka 6150	Taka 2,600	Taka 2,000	Taka 1,000	Taka 1,500	Taka 750	Taka 750
41.69 %	17.63 %	13.56 %	6.78 %	10.16%	5.09 %	5.09 %
Tour Operator	Transport (Dhaka – Bban - Dhaka)	Transport within Bandarban	Accommodation Ruma & beyond plus Accommodation Bandarban	Food Ruma and Bandarban	Guide Ruma	Out of Pocket Expenditure Ruma & Bandarban
Service Inputs. Intervention needed for good accommodation in Ruma and beyond, Good restaurants be established at Ruma and Boga Lake and other camping grounds. Trained Guide be prepared to add value, and availability of trekking equipment should be made locally.						

Strategies for the adventure tourism:

So the strategy for the adventure tourism (trekking and track tourism) should be:

- (i) There is a need for responsible guidelines for developing trekking routes and collaborating with local communities
- (ii) Accommodation facility for the trekkers should be improved and formalized so that the local people can earn more. At present the trekkers are accommodated in below standard tin-shed rest houses having no good facility for sleeping and wash room. In places the trekkers stay in the houses of the tribal people which some time may not be liked both by the tourists as well as the community people because (a) poor tribal people are not in a position to arrange for good accommodation by providing beds and other facilities, and (b) the tourists also want a bit comfortable night-stay after a whole-day trekking. Besides, the trekkers pointed out the absence of good wash rooms with which they are used. Rearing up the pet pigs sometimes is not well accepted by the plain land tourists. Consequently it is not realized by the local community that accommodation can also be a formal trade, rather they consider it as hospitality. So, for the night stay they formally do not charge any specific amount of money. It depends on the whims of the tourists how much to pay. Therefore, by upgrading night-stay facilities, some guidelines may be developed to fix up the prices for these services offered by the local community.
- (iii) At present the trekkers have to carry dry food and fruits as there exists no formal restaurant in the places where the trekkers have to take their lunch, dinner and breakfast. Some time they have to carry live chicks, eggs and request the local people to cook for them. Although there is no big difference in food menu of the tribal people and the plain land trekkers, but as of the process of preparing meals differs widely, the tourists can not enjoy the food to taste. Beside, use of same kitchen-wares sometimes make the trekkers fussy and fretful. So, establishment of separate restaurants in the proposed camp grounds and train the tribal girls in Bangla recipe could be good source of income for the local community. All the ingredients are available locally.
- (iv) Guiding has become a good source of income for the local youths. But the guides are all self-made and self-developed. They do not have formal training in guiding. So, if the quality of the guide services could be raised through training, the rate could be much higher benefitting the local youths. Now costs for guide services vary as per the number days for which the guides are hired and also the destinations selected. Presently as this service is not performed professionally, the trekkers observed that sometime the guides are not that much serious in providing their services. Besides, a guide line could be developed to establish a justified guide/tourist ratio depending on the number of tourists

in the group and the perils of the routes. It is to be noted here that for trekking the trekkers have to hire the guide services from Ruma only.

- (v) To diversify involvement of local community members in tourism, alternative activities can be considered. For example, cultural show by the tribal people could be arranged in places where the tourists and the trekkers have a night-stay. Cultural show at night could refresh the trekkers and the community could charge some fee for the show. The tribal community specially the Bawm, Marma, Tripura, Khyang and the Tonchangya people have rich cultural heritages. In many places of Bandarban, these communities perform the cultural program for the tourists for money. They also feel proud to exhibit their own cultural performances. Culture could be turned into a major tourism product in this hill district.
- (vi) At specific camping grounds, one shop could be established to sell the locally produced handicrafts, and also items needed for trekking.

In case of sunlust tourism, the following value chain analysis can give some idea about the avenues where the policy makers have to put more emphasis.

Table 9.2 : VALUE CHAIN MAP FOR BANDARBANNORMAL PACKAGE (sight seeing, Rest, Relax) EXPENDITURE.

Tourism Itinerary : Dhaka - Bandarban - Dhaka. (Typical Package : 3 nights 2 days)						
Total Tourist Expenditure on Excursion Experience = Taka 8,200 (per person)						
Published price of Excursion Package = Taka 6,000 (per person)						
Share of Tourist Expenditure						
Outside Bandarban = Taka 4000(48.78%)			Cost of Inputs within Bandarban (including Ruma) = Taka 4200 (51.22%)			
Taka 2800	Taka 1200	Taka 1,000	Taka 1,000	Taka 1,200	Taka 1000	Total Taka 8200
34.14 %	14.63 %	12.20 %	12.20 %	14.63%	12.20 %	(100%)
Tour Operator	Transport (Non AC, Dhaka – Bban– Dhaka)	Transport within Bandarban	Accommodation Bandarban (class Hotel)	Food Rumaand Bandarban	Out of Pocket Expenditure	Stay more nights Campaign be Launched.
Scope for Intervention						

From the figure it is quite clear that there are scopes for interventions in the activities of transport, accommodation, food, and shopping. The tourists who are having the motivation for sight-seeing and relaxation, naturally belong to quality tourist group. They want to stay in

quality accommodation units which preferably are at a remote area amidst the nature. They want to have good food in clean environment, they like to have a short trip to some nearby attractions by a good transport medium, they like to spend money for buying souvenirs or enjoying the local tribal cultural diversity. The Army resort at Nilgiri (around 45 kms away from Bandarban district town) is quite expensive, but throughout the year it remains booked, and it is not possible to get accommodation especially in tourist season at Nilgiri resort unless someone is lucky. The same picture could be found with 'Milan Chhari' and the 'Sakura' – two privately owned hill side beautiful resources (three kms away from the town).

Strategies for the sun lust tourism:

So the strategy for this segment of market should be:

- (i) Policy formulation to encourage the investors to build eco-resorts in natural setting. But as the outsiders cannot buy land in the hilly district, so at least some form of joint venture be initiated by the Hill district Council to attract the investors.
- (ii) Although there are almost 145 different types of old fashioned vehicles operating in different routes on regular basis, but for this segment of market, comfortable and hassle-free transport system should be encouraged to ply on the hilly roads. Local people should be encouraged to be involved in tourism business, especially in arranging the local tour programs where small itineraries be developed covering the attractions in and around Bandarabansadar town. In Ruma there is scope for business by a few number of local trekking operators.
- (iii) There are almost 20 local handicraft sales outlets. But many of these are selling goods directly brought from Myanmar illegally. In the town, there is a beautiful BSCIC sales centre too. PUNAK (Police women welfare) is also having a good sales centre in Bandarban. The resorts could be advised to create their own handicraft sales outlets within the premise. The resorts should be encouraged to support the local craftsmanship.
- (iv) An open air platform could be established in the town where the sunlust tourists can enjoy the tribal cultural performances at cost. The KhudraNrigoshthirSanskritik Institute (KSI) can come forward in arranging this sort of shows commercially.
- (v) The sunlust tourists should be motivated to spend more nights by developing several attractive small itineraries by the local tour operators. The resort owners can also help the tour operators developing these itineraries.

Role of agriculture in Bandarban tourism:

Figure 9.4: Role of agriculture in Bandarban tourism

Economy of Bandarban is still agriculture dominated. The people have to depend on widespread Jumm farming. However, Agri-products are produced little and mostly used for self-consumption of the hill people. Fruits (banana, pineapple, jackfruit, papaya), and spices (masala) like ginger, and turmeric are also produced in Bandarban. Recently many farmers have tilted towards cultivating more tobacco leaves; it being the main profitable cash crop. From the study it has been seen that only a few varieties of vegetables that are produced locally can meet a part of the existing market demand. Hilly chicks, beef and mutton is also supplied locally, but not enough to meet market demand. Some spices like ginger, turmeric, chilli etc. are also supplied locally. Beside, some fruits like banana, pine apples, mango, and cashew nuts are also supplied to the market. But the quantity of production is not enough to establish large scale processing plants. However, the local community members can crush the fruits by small crushers and make the juices of different fruits available to the tourists. Separate study is needed to identify the role of agro-products in total tourism business in Bandarban.

**ACTION PLAN MATRIX: INTERVENTIONS AND IMPLEMENTATION
(As per Specific Value Chains/Activities)**

Value Chain/ Activities	Challenges for tourism development in Bandarban and Ruma	Interventions	Time frame	Implementing Agencies
Accommodation	Growth of unplanned & sub- standard hotels	Needs to develop a total plan for Bandarban town as well as whole of the district.	Continuous (immediate to start)	MoCHTA, BTB, CHTRC, BHDC,
	Crisis in Finance	Provision for tourism loan for hoteliers	Short and Long term	Govt. and Private Banks
	Poor service standard	Training to hotel service personnel	Continuously for Short and Long term	BPC(NHTTI) / ICIMOD
	Below standard rest houses/tin-shed cottage having no good facility for sleeping and wash room in Ruma, Boga Lake, and Keokradong. that demotivate quality tourist group (sunlust tourists)	Policy formulation to encourage the investors to develop quality accommodation units (Eco-resort and camping grounds) in natural setting.	In earlier stage of tourism development	CHTRC/BHDC/ICIMOD/PPP
	Shortage in electricity supply	Increasing electricity supply to meet the increased demand specially in tourist season	Short and long run.	PDB/BHDC/CHTDB (study could be conducted to assess feasibility of producing electricity there)
	Shortage in water supply	Establishing water treatment plant from Sangu	2-3 years	CHTBD/BHDC/Public Health Department, GoB.
	Transportation	Poor Condition of Road from Ruma to Boga Lake	Renovating road from Ruma to Boga Lake. Construct the road from Ruma bridge to Ruma bazar.	2 years
Safety and security risk		Ensuring security by assigning tourist police/law enforcing agencies in distant tourist spots	1 year to establish facilities and then continuous	BGB/ Bangladesh Police/CHTRC/ BHDC
Old fashioned and uncomfortable vehicles operating in different routes		Comfortable and hassle-free mode of transport be encouraged to ply. Fashionable & comfortable engine boats be put into Sangu river	In earlier stage of tourism development	Private sector investors/ Tour operators/ Local people

		for track tourism		
Restaurant	Poor quality food and food safety	Training on food preparation, hygiene and law relating to food safety & restaurant	Continuously	BPC (NHTTI) ICIMOD
		• Monitoring	Continuously	• Local Administration
	Crisis in Finance	Provision for soft loan for creation of restaurants/food shops	Short and Long term	Govt. and Private Banks/
	Lack of ethnic restaurant Bandarban Sadar and Ruma Bazar area	Promoting and helping tribal people establish ethnic restaurant in Bandarban Sadar and Ruma and elsewhere in the district serving tribal foods hygienically	1 year	UNDP/ ICIMOD
	Poor decoration and unclean ambiances in restaurant	Initiating for minimum decoration & maintaining cleanliness	Short and Long term	Restaurant owners/ Local Administration
Trekking / Track tourism/ Excursion	No clear idea about the track tourism and trekking opportunity in Bandarban	Preparing a comprehensive list of Track tourism & trekking trails & routes for Ruma, Thanchi, Bandarban	2-3 years	Local tour guide association ICIMOD BPC Dept. of Tourism and Hospitality Management, Dhaka University
	No formal provision for accommodation at different points of existing trekking trails	Developing Camping Ground/home stay facility at Different night halting Trekking Points as suggested in the report	2-3 years	MoCHTA/BHDC/BTB / ICIMOD/ Local tribes
	No formal provision for food & beverage at different points of existing trekking trails	Establishing mini restaurant in tribal village/camping grounds in the trekking routes run by the villagers as suggested in the report Training on cooking and serving food to them	2-3 years	MoCHTA/ BHDC/BPC/ ICIMOD
	No organized contribution to the income of the tribal people from tribal cultural show and handicrafts	Establishing handicraft sales outlets in the Camping Ground Open air platform to be established in the Camping Ground as well as in the town	2-3 years	BHDC/KSI/ ICIMOD/ BSCIC

	Tour operators are not aware of the tourism product in Bandarban	Promoting trekking trails in Ruma, Thanchi, Bandarban tonational and international tour operators. Preparing creative media for relaying information to tour operators (e.g. picturesque map).	In earlier stage of tourism development	BHDC/BPC/BTB/MoCHTA/MoCAT/ICIMOD
	Lack of promotional activity regarding track tourism & trekking in Bandarban	Promotional campaign to make people know about the trekking & track routes and opportunity	Continuously	MoCHTA/BHDC/BTB/MoCAT
Handicraft	Seasonality of demand	Establishing sales outlet in Dhaka and Chittagong and Cox's Bazar	1-2 year	ICIMOD/ BSCIC/ UNDP/NGOs
	Lack of business knowledge of the craftsmen	Training on business knowledge	2-3 years	ICIMOD/ BSCIC/ UNDP
	Very low level of out of pocket spending on shopping	Market research to determine customer requirement. Designing and producing products according to the market demand.		ICIMOD/ BSCIC/Dept. of Tourism and Hospitality Management, Dhaka University
	Low level of involvement of individual craftsmen with tourism specially those having no shop in market & living in remote tribal villages	Establishing handicraft sales outlets in the Camping Ground at Different night halting Trekking & track trail Points as suggested in the report	2-3 years	ICIMOD/Local tribal community/ BHDC
Planning, Marketing, Promotion, and Research	Scattered tourism development	Formulating and implementing Tourism Master Plan for Bandarban	Master plan For 5 years	BTB/CHTRC/BHDC/MoCHTA, ICIMOD, Dept. of Tourism, DU.
	Need for tourism brand and marketing plan	Integrated tourism marketing plan to promote and develop Bandarban for adventure tourism	Short and Long term	BPC/ BTB/BHDC/MoCHTA/ MoCAT
	Need for specific short term activity plan	Tourism carrying capacity assessment of trekking and track tourism routes, determining Limit of Acceptable Change (LAC) in tourism development etc. in Ruma and other areas of Bandarban	1 year	BTB/MoCHTA/MoCAT/ Dept of Tourism, DU

Public Private Partnership	Difficulties in investment as outsiders cannot buy land in the hilly district	Policy formulation to encourage the investors to build eco-resorts in natural setting. At least some form of joint venture should be initiated by the Hill district Council to attract the investors. Other innovative means to bring on board investors can be explored.	In earlier stage of tourism development	CHTRC/ BHDC/ MoCHTA
	Threat for ecological imbalance	Making people aware about sustainable eco-tourism in a collaborative manner	Continuously	Tour operators/local community/ local administration/BHDC /other stakeholders

Chapter 10

Involving the Local Ethnic Groups directly with Tourism

Probably the easiest way to involve the local people with tourism and hospitality is initially to create some camping grounds in some of the trekking and Track tourism points where the tourists and the trekkers have to spend nights and in day time have to take lunch. The concept of camping grounds is comparatively new in Bangladesh. It is a premise where there could be platforms to mount the tents. The tents are not permanent. Whenever asked for, the tents instantly could be mounted. Within the premise there should be a restaurant (dining space), washing facilities and toilets, an open air a bit alleviated stage for performance by the tribal people or by the trekkers themselves, may be a watch tower for spending some time viewing the serene beauty of the hills, and one or two cottages built for the trek leaders or for the quality tourists (A very successful camping ground named 'ChhayaGiri' has been created by the Bandarban Police in Bandarban town and the Superintendent of Police told us that during tourist season this camping ground remains booked althrough).

These trekking rest points (camping grounds) should be located at spaces nearby the small ethnic "para" (village). The whole community should be involved in establishing, running, and maintaining the camping grounds. The "Sardar" (leader) of the community will be responsible for coordination.

The cost of creating such type of camping ground is around 500 thousand Taka only, however, which is quite difficult to be borne by the poor tribal community. So for this capital investment some donor agencies like ICIMOD, UNDP, ADB, or MoCHTA, BDHC, CHTDB etc. may be approached.

Different facilities for the trekkers and the tourists in one camping ground may include:

1. Platform for mounting tents: tents, mattresses and other sleeping objects will be supplied by the community. In exchange they will charge reasonable tariff from the tourists
2. Establishment of bamboo, wood and tin-shed (or thatched) resorts : the trekking team leaders/group leaders who expect a better place to spend night, could be accommodated in these eco-resorts. The charge will be higher than the tents.
3. Dinning facility: for breakfast, lunch, dinner, tea etc. a beautifully decorated open restaurant type establishment with local motifs could be built. Trained household cooks may supply foods as per the taste of the tourists. Charge could be a bit high.
4. Open-air stage: a multipurpose open air stage should be created for performing arts by the local ethnic performers as well as the tourists. Depending on early intimation, the community leader may arrange the ethnic performances for which the tourist group could be charged a reasonable amount of money. In tourist season, this sort of performance could be made compulsory and the cost could be included in the package.
5. A small handicraft shop could be established in the camping ground: the local craftsmanship could be displayed there and the tourists should be motivated to buy the items.
6. The camping ground must have wash and toilet facility: water being scarce in supply on top of the hills, the tourists could be charged for use of this facility.

Earning through a camping ground could be shared by the members of the community who is maintaining the camp ground. In this way there could be a sudden uplift of income among the ethnic tribal groups.

The following figure shows an imaginary layout of a camping ground:

Figure 10.1: Proposed layout of a Camping Ground.

Proposal for trekking and trek tourism development

In the following sections, we propose some of the widely used trekking and track tourism routes which are known to the tourists. These are the examples and by doing a massive survey several adventurous routes could be identified.

Proposal # 1: Trekking

Dhaka-Bandarban-BoroMowdok (Jungle visit by boat) Duration: 6 nights 5 days

Brief Description of the trail:

One will enjoy a lot of attractions in this trail. This is called the most risky and most beautiful trail in Bangladesh. The boat journey is fantastic through the hilly Sangu river. Stones of giant sizes will be seen in this trail. Different famous stones are given different names like BORO PATHOR, RANIR SIRI etc. The bird named Sarosh (crane) which is in the threat of extinction can only be seen here. Night in the tribal village will also be a memorable part of the journey. Nafakhum is one of the most attractive waterfalls of Bangladesh. It is called the Niagra of Bangladesh.

Figure : Trekking Route: Dhaka – Bandarban – Boro Mowdok

Trail direction:

Note: During the forwarding journey the boat goes against the current, for this reason it takes more time than the return journey to pass same distance.

Pictures of the Trail:

Source: Banglatrek.org

Facilities to develop:

Food & Beverage: At Thanchi, BoroMowdok, Tindu, Remakri & Tinkhamukhpara.

Accommodation: At Thanchi, BoroMowdok, Tindu & Remakri.

Cultural Program: At Thanchi, BoroMowdok, Tindu & Remakri.

Figure 10.2: Map of the trail:

Figure 10.3: Map is Drawn from Google Earth

THE PROACTIVE ROLES OF ICIMOD, DIFFERENT GOVERNMENT AGENCIES, AND THE PRIVATE SECTOR (Specific actions needed from specific parties) :

1. ICIMOD :

Tourism Development Activities	Intervention by ICIMOD	Time frame	Resources needed	Focus Groups and Beneficiaries
Identifying different new Trekking routes in Ruma (covering Thanchi)	Providing services of Trekking experts for conducting survey	1 year (covering both winter and monsoon season)	Consultancy services from experienced Trekkers	Adventure tourists as a whole. The local community at the end.
Improvement of the existing trekking routes (for Ruma and Thanchi)	Providing services of trekking experts	Continuous throughout the project period	Experienced trekking organizations (may be from Nepal), necessary equipment, materials, plans etc.	Tourists and the local community
Creation of Camping grounds at certain points of the routes (Ruma and Thanchi)	Providing/managing funds	Continuous throughout the project period	Financing the purchase of materials for creation of camp ground, indigenous resorts (made of bamboo and woods), and other facilities.	Local people financially, and the tourists by receiving comfortable services.
Creation of Groups within the community who will operate and manage the camping grounds in long run (Ruma and Thanchi)	Organizing groups with the remote ethnic people along the trekking routes	Continuous throughout the project period.	Motivational campaign among the tribal groups. Services of the heads of the groups, Local administration, NGOs	Ethnic people (making aware about alternative sources of earning)
Training to run the Camping grounds	Developing manuals and organizing training	Continuous throughout the	Marketing experts, local	Ethnic groups (Ruma and

commercially	programs	project period	administration, NGOs	Thanchi)
Training to the Guides	Developing manuals and organizing training programs	3 – 6 months	Tourist Guide organizations	Ethnic young people(Ruma and Thanchi)
Hospitality and Catering training	Developing manuals and organizing training programs, or NHTTI of the BPC could be engaged	1 – 2 years	On-field training program. Trainer(s), materials etc. are needed. NHTTI or any private training institute may supply.	Ethnic people, mainly women. (Ruma and Thanchi)
Training for making varieties of handicraft products, Products needed for trekking	Contacting BSCIC for developing training manuals	Continuous throughout the project period	Training manuals and materials	Ethnic women (Ruma and Thanchi)
Marketing of these products	Creation of small showrooms at the premise of Camping grounds. Contacting the big NGO sales outlets in Dhaka and other places to seek help in marketing the products.	1 – 2 years	Little amount of funds may be required.	Ethnic women (Ruma and Thanchi)
Making fruit juice	Can help improving indigenous method of making juice	1 -2 years	Supply of small manual juicers	Ethnic women, farmers (Ruma and Thanchi)
Making power available in the camping grounds	Financing solar panels	Throughout the project period	Solar panels	Tourists

2. The Government Agencies :

Tourism Development Activities	Intervention by Different govt. agencies	Time frame	Resources needed	Focus Groups and Beneficiaries
Inviting big investment in tourism (State-of-art hill resorts around Bandarbandsadar, Ruma, Thanchi, Alikadam)	MoCHTA	Continuous	Capital investment (to create state-of-art hilly resorts, restaurant, eco-parks with amusement facilities like the 'Meghla'.	Local people, tourists
Developing Transport facilities (roads)	MoCHTA, Dept. of Environment, CHTDB, LGED, Local administrative agencies.	Continuous	Mainly finance, technical knowhow.	Local people, tourists
Developing supply of Electricity facility	PDB, REB, CHTDB, Dept. of Environment, BUET, CUET	Continuous	Finance and technical knowhow.	Local people, tourists
Promotion of Tourism of Bandarban	BHDC, MoCHTA, BTB, BPC	Continuous	Finance and technical knowhow (Advertising firms, TV channels).	Stakeholders of Bandarban tourism
Collection of Tourism Data	BHDC, Bandarban Police, Accommodation units in the district, BTB, BBS, DTHM, DU	Continuous	Technical knowhow, computer networking, questionnaire development	Overall Tourism of Bandarban.
Supply of water	BHDC, Public Health Dept, BUET, CUET, Environment Dept.	Continuous	Technical knowhow, consultancy	Local people, tourists, Overall tourism of Bandarban
Maintenance of Law and order situation (safety and security of tourists)	Bangladesh Police(may be Hill Tourist police),Community Police	Continuous	Government intention and planning	Tourists, local people, entrepreneurs

3. PPP

Tourism Development Activities	Intervention by different parties	Time frame	Resources needed	Focus Groups and Beneficiaries
Establishing hilly resort around Bandarbandsadar for the sun lust tourists	BHDC, Big investors experienced in tourism	Continuous	Finance, technical knowhow, trained and skilled Human resource,	Local people, sun lust tourists
Establishing small tourism related business units including processing plants for agri-items.	Private and Public Banks	Continuous	Financing loans to the local entrepreneurs	Local people
Maintain Sustainability (protecting nature and environment)	BHDC, ICIMOD, MoCHTA, BTB, Dept. of Environment, Tour Operators, Local community, Bandarban Police, Local administration including Municipality office, Hoteliers' association.	Continuous	Finance is needed	The Hill district of Bandarban, the tourism treasure of Bandarban, Image of Bangladesh

CONCLUSION

Bandarban is a unique destination for the travellers, especially the domestic travellers. It has been estimated that around 0.7 million tourists visit Bandarban each year who spend almost 100 crore BDT, or equivalent to 12.5 million USD there. The main objectives of the visit were relax & recreation, and adventure. However, Bandarban seemed to be more popular for adventure tourism which mainly comprise with trekking.

At present very few number of basic tourism based infrastructure and superstructure have been developed by any agency including the government. Road communication is very undeveloped and unpleasant. Only a few number of hotels and hill-side resorts have been developed by the private entrepreneurs. The local tribal people try to provide the accommodation and other facilities for the tourists who brave to penetrate into impassable areas as a part of their trekking exercise. Many tourists have to arrange for their own accommodation by carrying tents. The tribal people are not trained in hospitality. They do not have access to capital for establishing ecology- friendly cottages and other facilities for the tourists.

Few years before, there had been some insurgency problems in the hill districts which restricted the free entrance and movement of the civilians from other areas. Consequently, the enormous tourism sector of the area was untapped. However, with the enactment of Peace Accord in 1997, the domestic tourists were allowed to get in up to certain spatial radius. At present the situation has been much improved and the domestic visitors are allowed to go into remote areas of hill districts.

Regarding the investment climate in tourism sector, till now much favorable situation could not be seen because of two reasons mainly:

- (a) Before 1997 Peace Accord, economic and business activities were almost at a halt, and
- (b) After 1997 Peace Accord, the land management including sale, purchase, lease, transfer etc. has been vested in the hands of the District Council.

The land management provision of the accord does not encourage the investors to come up with big investment in economic and business sectors including tourism. As a result, the hill district, having greater opportunity for establishing SMEs in the fields of food processing, tourism and travelling, transportation, handicrafts and souvenir, accommodation etc., is lagging behind.

The district and local administration of Bandarban seems to be tourism-friendly. But due to government tradition and policy along with lack of experience and expertise, coupled with fund crisis, the local administration cannot play vital role in developing this tremendously potential sector in the hill district. The local tribal and Bengali people are also very poor

(Bandarban ranks 2nd in the list of most poverty stricken districts of Bangladesh). So these poor and mostly illiterate people do not have the capability to develop tourism establishments and run these with minimum professional standard.

Consequently, intervention is needed from outside in the fields of formulating tourism planning, creating eco-friendly infrastructure and superstructure, training the people in hospitality, making them innovative in exploring and exploiting varied income generating tourism and tourism related activities.

Considering the hyper-sensitive state of affairs in these hill districts, the Ministry of Chittagong Hill Tracts Affairs along with the Hill District Council can be the main actors for developing tourism sector there. ICIMOD and other donor agencies may channelize their expertise along with initially required fund through the Ministry. However, it would be courteous to involve the Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism, and the honorable King of Bandarban in this process.

A highly develop professional plan along with concerted efforts by the intervening agencies, in association with the local people's involvement, may metamorphose Bandarban into one of the most attractive tourism destinations of south Asian region.

References and Bibliographies

Afroz, N. N., & Hasanuzzaman, Md. (2012). Problems and Prospects of Tourism in Bangladesh: Bandarban District Case. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research* Volume 12 Issue 23 Version 1.0 Year 2012. Publisher: Global Journals Inc. (USA)

ANNEX1:Some Selected Value Chain Mappings:

(i) Handicraft Value Chain map in Bandarban

Source : Field Data and information

(ii) RESTAURANT VALUE CHAIN MAP IN BANDARBAN

(iii) Value Chain Mapping for Excursion in Bandarban

(iv) Value Chain Mapping for Accommodation in Bandarban

ANNEX2: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents:

(i) Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (Bandarban)

Gender (Bandarban)		
Gender	Frequency	Percent
female	4	7.4%
male	50	92.6%
Total	54	100.0%

Age range (Bandarban)		
Age range	Frequency	Percent
15-24	18	33.33
25-34	32	59.26
45-54	4	7.41
Total	54	100.0

Occupation (Bandarban)		
Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Student	22	40.74
full time employed	26	48.15
Businessman	6	11.11
Total	54	100.0

(ii) Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (Ruma)

Gender (Ruma)		
Gender	Frequency	Percent
female	0	0%
male	22	100%
Total	22	100.0%

Age range (Ruma)		
Age range	Frequency	Percent
15-24	2	9
25-34	16	73
45-54	4	18
Total	22	100.0

Occupation (Ruma)		
Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Student	2	9
full time employed	14	64
Businessman	6	27
Total	22	100.0

ANNEX3: Descriptive and Correlation Analysis of Motivating Factors:

Descriptive Analysis of Motivating Factors (Bandarban)

Descriptive Statistics

		HILL_FOR	PEACE	NATURE	ETHNICUL	ADVENTUR	FAMILY
N	Valid	51	52	52	54	54	50
	Missing	3	2	2	0	0	4
Mean		4.69	4.46	4.62	4.04	4.48	2.60
Median		5.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	2.00
Mode		5	5	5	4	5	2
Std. Deviation		.547	.641	.565	.751	.746	1.457

Correlation Analysis of Motivating Factors (Bandarban)

Correlations

		HILL_FOR	PEACE	NATURE	ETHNICUL	ADVENTUR	FAMILY
HILL_FOR	Pearson Correlation	1	.750(**)	.622(**)	.115	.292(*)	-.298(*)
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.421	.038	.040
	N	51	50	50	51	51	48
PEACE	Pearson Correlation	.750(**)	1	.608(**)	.339(*)	.222	-.095
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.014	.113	.510
	N	50	52	52	52	52	50
NATURE	Pearson Correlation	.622(**)	.608(**)	1	.261	.633(**)	.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.062	.000	1.000
	N	50	52	52	52	52	50
ETHNICUL	Pearson Correlation	.115	.339(*)	.261	1	.506(**)	.125
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.421	.014	.062	.	.000	.388
	N	51	52	52	54	54	50
ADVENTUR	Pearson Correlation	.292(*)	.222	.633(**)	.506(**)	1	.008
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.038	.113	.000	.000	.	.956
	N	51	52	52	54	54	50
FAMILY	Pearson Correlation	-.298(*)	-.095	.000	.125	.008	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.040	.510	1.000	.388	.956	.
	N	48	50	50	50	50	50

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Descriptive Analysis of Motivating Factors (Ruma)

Statistics

		HILL_FOR	PEACE	NATURE	ETHNICUL	ADVENTUR	FAMILY
N	Valid	21	20	20	22	22	18
	Missing	1	2	2	0	0	4
Mean		4.81	4.30	4.50	3.64	4.36	2.33
Median		5.00	4.00	4.50	4.00	5.00	2.00
Mode		5	4	4(a)	3(a)	5	1(a)
Std. Deviation		.402	.657	.513	.658	.790	1.372

a Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

Correlation Analysis of Motivating Factors (Ruma)

Correlations

		HILL_FOR	PEACE	NATURE	ETHNICUL	ADVENTUR	FAMILY
HILL_FOR	Pearson Correlation	1	.625(**)	.000	-.252	-.381	.134
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.003	1.000	.271	.089	.597
	N	21	20	20	21	21	18
PEACE	Pearson Correlation	.625(**)	1	.156	-.024	-.349	.375
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.	.511	.919	.131	.125
	N	20	20	20	20	20	18
NATURE	Pearson Correlation	.000	.156	1	-.156	.447(*)	.783(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000	.511	.	.511	.048	.000
	N	20	20	20	20	20	18
ETHNICUL	Pearson Correlation	-.252	-.024	-.156	1	.267	-.177
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.271	.919	.511	.	.230	.483
	N	21	20	20	22	22	18
ADVENTUR	Pearson Correlation	-.381	-.349	.447(*)	.267	1	.203
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.089	.131	.048	.230	.	.420
	N	21	20	20	22	22	18
FAMILY	Pearson Correlation	.134	.375	.783(**)	-.177	.203	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.597	.125	.000	.483	.420	.
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

ANNEX4: Proposed trekking and track tourism routes:

Proposal # 2: (Trekking)

Dhaka- Bandarban-Bolipara- Ri Sung Sung

Duration: 3 nights 2 days

Brief Description of the trail:

This trail is developed basically keeping in mind the need of the trekker who have a very short time like 2 nights-1 day or 3 nights-2 days. Ri Sung Sung is a 30-40 feet high waterfall not known by many. There is a tribal village on the way from Bolipara Bazar to Ri Sung Sung named CHO CHU PARA. It is a Marma village. The night in the village and the virgin waterfall give simply an awesome experience.

Trail Direction:

Here: B = Breakfast. D = Dinner L = Lunch and C = Cultural program

Picture of the waterfall: *Photo Credit: Zakiul Deep, Banglatrek.org*

Map to go to the Waterfall:

(Map to go to Ri Sung Sung)

UPAZILA MAP UPAZILA THANCHI DISTRICT BANDARBAN

LEGEND

- Administrative Boundary**
 - International Boundary
 - District Boundary
 - Upazila Boundary
 - Union Boundary
 - Mauza Boundary
 - Municipal Boundary
- Administrative Headquarters**
 - District
 - Upazila
 - Union
- Physical Infrastructures**
 - National Highways
 - Regional Highways
 - Zila Road
 - Upazila Road (Pucca)
 - Upazila Road (Katcha)
 - Union Road (Pucca)
 - Union Road (Katcha)
 - Village Road A (Pucca)
 - Village Road A (Katcha)
 - Village Road B (Pucca)
 - Village Road B (Katcha)
 - Railway Network
 - Embankment
- Natural Features**
 - Wide River with Sandy Area
 - Small River/ Khal
 - Water Bodies
 - Forest
 - Hill
- Socio-Economic Infrastructures**
 - Growth Centre
 - Rural Market
 - Police Station
 - Upazila Health Complex
 - Family welfare Centre
 - Community Clinic
 - Post Office
 - College
 - High School
 - Primary School
 - Madrasa
 - Mosque
 - Ashrayan/Abasan
 - Settlement

Trail Direction:
 Trekking Route From Balipara Bazar to Ri Sung Sung
 Ri Sung Sung Waterfall

Disclaimer : Information theme contained in this map sheet is only for internal use of Local Government Engineering Department. Information theme of this map sheet is not authoritative for any other use.
 Compiled from : LGED Upazila Base Maps 1994-05, Landsat TM 1998, GPS Survey 1999 and Field Checking in 2010
 Projection : Lambert's Conformal Conic
 PREPARED BY : GIS UNIT
 LOCAL GOVERNMENT ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

SCALE
 1 : 2,25,000

Source: Map is developed by the team

Map is drawn from the Google Earth by the team

Facilities to be developed:

Accommodation: At Chu Cho Para
Beverage: At Chu Cho Para
Cultural Program: At Chu Cho Para

Food &

Proposal 3: (Track Tourism)

Dhaka- Bandarban-Ruma-Boga Lake

Duration: 3 nights 2 days

Brief Description of the trail:

It is the mostly used trekking trail which can be converted to track tourism by developing and providing relatively more facilities to lessen the hardship of the tourists who fear to trek. It is also the most popular trail which consists of one lake and one peak. But we have considered the zone up to Boga lake for track tourism . If someone wants to cover Keokradong, s/he can easily do it after a night stay at Bogalake. This trail gives the tourist a panoramic view of HillyBogalake. And the journey with “chandergari” (old jeep) will also be a memorable one.

Trail Direction:

Facilities needed to be developed:Accommodation: At Boga Lake

Food & Beverage: At Boga Lake

Cultural Program: At Boga Lake

Map of the Trail to Boga Lake:

Map to go to Boga Lake drawn from Google Earth:

Pictures of Boga Lake:

Photo Credit: Banglatrek.org

ANNEX5: List of Key People Interviewed during the field survey from 14th August, 2013 to 28th August, 2013:

Name	Organization/Company
1. Mr. KyawShweHla	Honorable Chairman, Bandarban Hill District Council (BHDC), Bandarban Sadar, Bandarban.
2. Mr. Bikash Chandra Sikdar	Chief Executive Officer, Bandarban Hill District Council (BHDC), Bandarban Sadar, Bandarban.
3. Mr. KamrulAhsan	Superintendent of Police, Bandarban Hill District, Bandarban.
4. Md. Nurul Amin Chowdhury	Secretary, Bandarban Chamber of Commerce and Industry.
5. Mrs. LalSaniLushei	President, Bandarban Woman Chamber of Commerce and Industry.
6. Mr. Serajul Islam	President, Bandarban Hotel, Motel, Guest house Owners' Association, Bandarban.
7. Mr. GiasUddin Master	President, Bandarban Restaurant Owners' Association, Bandarban.
8. Mr. Amol Das	General Secretary, Bandarban Bus Owners' Association, Bandarban.
9. Mr. Md. Abdur Rashid	Joint Secretary, Bandarban Jeep – Car – Microbus Owners' Association, Bandarban.
10. Mr. Md. ZakirHossain	Officer-in-Charge, Ruma Police Station, Ruma.
11. Mr. Md. JasimUddin	Line-man, Speed Boat Owners' Association of Ruma, Ruma, Bandarban.
12. Mr. Vinod	Line-man, Ruma Jeep Owners' Association, Ruma, Bandarban.
13. Mr. V T Bawm	General Secretary, Young Bawm Association, Ruma.
14. Mr. FaridulHaque	Managing Director, Tour Planners Ltd (Tour Operator). Former President, Tour Operator Association of Bangladesh (TOAB)
15. Md. Musa KalimullahKislu	Owner, Sakura Hill Resort, Bandarban. Executive Director, Bangladesh Water Society.

**ANNEX6: LIST OF PARTICIPANTS IN STAKEHOLDERS' MEETING
AT RUMA ON 6th OCTOBER, 2013:**

Sl.	Name	Profession	Cell phone
1	Vannun Siam Bawm	Organizer	01552341753
2	Md. Faridul Alam	Police Officer	01817734180
3	Jahangir Alam	Special Branch	01718737471
4	Sankar Das	Hotelier	01553105875
5	William Marma	Lineman	01553105903
6	Vanrem Lal Bawm	Business	01554791613
7	Selim Uddin	Agriculture	
8	Chandan Karmakar	Small trade	
9	Samuel Bawm	Local govt. employee	01557667718
10	Panuam Bawm	Organizer	01557764137
11	Thanku Khumi	Asst. Teacher	01552386443
12	Palash Chowdhury	Ward member	01784527042
13	Lelung Khumi	Asst. Teacher	01840720802
14	Jingermoy Bawm	Asst. Teacher	01552609968
15	Beng Em Moy Bawm	Agriculture	01556599411
16	Lalpiang Thang Bawm	Agriculture	01557655120
17	Lalcheo Sang	Headman	--
18	Nurul Islam	Driver	
19	Jouthan Moy Bawm	--	--
20	Joy pana Barua		
21	Ranjit Barua	Hotelier	
22	Binod Karmakar		
23	Abdur Rashid	Hotelier	
24	Md. Abul Kashem	Driver	
25	Kwaimajui Marma	Small trader	
26	Md Hazrat Ali	Small Trader	
27	Keji Bawm	Day Laborer	
28	Don trong	Service	
29	Peklian Bawm	Service	
30	Lal Dumang Bawm	Agriculture related	
31	Lallian Thang Lusai	Agri related trade	
32	Rialdao Bawm	Horticulture	
33	Lalnun Noam	Gardener	
34	Abdus Salam	Small trader	
35	Aungthowai Ching Marma	Chairman, Ruma subdistrict Parishad	01556742536
36	Shingla Ching Marma	Journalist	
37	Sang Muam Bawm	President Young Bawm Association (YBA)	
38	Viti Bawm	VP, YBA	

ANNEX7: Questionnaires

Tourism Assessment Survey (Bandarban) 2013
Survey Questionnaire (Tourist)

Name..... Cell/Phone.....

E-mail/ Address.....

Sec 1: Establishing the individual visitor profile

1.1 Who has organized your tour to Bandarban?

- Self Package tour Operator Others (Corporate, Club)

1.2. What mode of transportation did you use?

- Air Bus Car Rail

1.3. What types of accommodations do you use in the area? campsites guesthouses

- hotels resorts others

1.4. How many nights you stay in Bandarban?

- 0 (day visitor) 1 night 2-3 nights 4-7 nights

1.5. How many people, including yourself, are in your immediate party?

- Single 2-5 6-10 11-15 more _____

1.6. What is the main purpose of your visit?

- Leisure, recreation and holiday
 Visiting friends and relatives
 Business and professional
 Adventure
 Religion/pilgrimages
 Other _____

1.7. Are you visiting-?

- Bandarban only
- Circuit tour: Fromto – Bandarban – to

Sec 2: Evaluating the Potential of the Site

2.1. Will you come back to the site in the future? Yes No

2.2. Will you recommend the name of Bandarban to someone else? Yes No

2.3. Do you think the accommodation facility (guesthouse, hotel and restaurant) in Bandarban is satisfying? Yes No

2.4. Is the transportation facility (to and within) Bandarban is satisfying- Yes No

Sec 3:

Why did you select Bandarban to visit (motivation)?-

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
For seeing the hills and forest	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For sensing peace and quiet	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For enjoying the natural environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For knowing local/ethnic culture	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For adventure activities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
For spending time with family	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Sec 4: Approximately how much was your budget for travelling Bandarban?

Expenditure Heads	Amount (Percentage)
6. Accommodation	
7. Food	
8. Transport (local)	
9. Buying local products (handicrafts)	
10. Others	

Sec 5: Personal questions

Are you:

- Female Male

What is your age range?

- 15-24 25-34 35-44 45-54 55-64 65 and above

What is your marital status?

- Single Married

Please indicate which of the following categories applies to you:

- full-time employee (more than 30 hours a week)
 student
 unemployed
 homemaker
 other (please specify) ____

Thank You for Your Cordial Help

Tourism Assessment Survey (Bandarban/Ruma) 2013 Survey Questionnaire (Restaurant)

Organization			
Address			
Ownership	Public	Private	Other
Target Market	Domestic	International	Religious All

Describe the food and beverage items which you sell.

What requirements do your buyers have?

--

Are you aware of international/national standards and regulations for your field of business (e.g. ISO norms, GAP, GMP, quality standards and laws, etc.?)

No	Yes (describe these)
----	----------------------

What is the price to which you sell one item (or the price for your 3-5 main items)?

--

What are your 3-5 main cost factors? Give an estimate on how much you spend on them

--

Number of Employees

Round the year		On season	
Indigenous	Non-indigenous	Indigenous	Non-indigenous

Do you think the number of people employed at accommodations will increase, decrease or stay the same in the next three years?

What are the greatest challenges you face in developing your BUSINESS:(Identify 2-3 major constraints)

- a.
- b.
- c.

What should be done to overcome these difficulties?

- a.
- b.
- c.

Tourism Assessment Survey (Bandarban/Ruma) 2013 Survey Questionnaire (Local Transportation)

Organization			
Address			
Ownership	Public	Private	Other
Target Market	Domestic	International	Religious All
Number of your-	Vehicle:		Sit:
Average Rate	Route		Rate (per person)

Are more transportation needed? Yes No

Number of Employees

Round the year		On season	
Indigenous	Non-indigenous	Indigenous	Non-indigenous

Do you think the number of people employed at accommodations will increase, decrease or stay the same in the next three years?

What are the greatest challenges you face in developing your BUSINESS in the Accommodation industry:(Identify 2-3 major constraints)

- a.
- b.
- c.

What should be done to overcome these difficulties?

- a.
- b.
- c.

Tourism Assessment Survey (Bandarban/Ruma) 2013 Survey Questionnaire (Accommodation)

Organization

Address

Ownership

Public	Private	Other
--------	---------	-------

Target Market

Domestic	International	Religious	All
----------	---------------	-----------	-----

Number of Bed

Room Rate

Occupancy Rate

Peak season (%):	Off-peak season (%):
------------------	----------------------

Occupancy Rate by year (%)

	2010	2011	2012

Are more accommodations needed? Yes No

Number of Employees

Round the year		On season	
Indigenous	Non-indigenous	Indigenous	Non-indigenous

Do you think the number of people employed at accommodations will increase, decrease or stay the same in the next three years?

What are the greatest challenges you face in developing your BUSINESS in the Accommodation industry:(Identify 2-3 major constraints)

- a.
- b.
- c.

What should be done to overcome these difficulties?

- a.
- b.
- c.

Tourism Assessment Survey (Bandarban/Ruma) 2013 Survey Questionnaire (Souvenirs/Handicrafts)

Organization

Address

Ownership

Public	Private	Other
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Target Market

Domestic	International	Religious	All
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Do your tourists buy handicrafts? If so, which products?

Is the demand for each type of handicraft increasing, decreasing or staying the same?

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Is there more demand than supply? Yes No

Why tourists buy such handicrafts (*strength*: design, quality, uniqueness etc.)?

--

What are the products *weaknesses* in specific?

--

Number of Employees

Round the year		On season	
Indigenous	Non-indigenous	Indigenous	Non-indigenous

Do you think the number of people employed at accommodations will increase, decrease or stay the same in the next three years?

What are the greatest challenges you face in developing your BUSINESS:(Identify 2-3 major constraints)

- a.
- b.
- c.

What should be done to overcome these difficulties?

- a.
- b.
- c.

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